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TA'LIM JARAYONINI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI

Rahimova Charos Odiljonovna
O'ZDJTU talabasi

Annotatsiya: Insoniyat taraqqiyotining hozirgi bosqichi globallashuv jarayonlarining jadal rivojlanishi orqali tavsiflanadi. Globallashuvni iqtisodiy jihatdan qaraydigan bo'lsak, u jahon xo'jaligining butun makonini qamrab oluvchi iqtisodiy munosabatlar tizimining tashkil topishi va rivojlanishini anglatadi.

Shu bois globallashuv sharoitlarida mustaqil ravishda qaror qabul qila oladigan, maqsadlarni belgilay oladigan va amalga oshira oladigan, o'z faoliyatni ongli baholay oladigan faol shaxsni shakllantirish muammosi dolzarb bo'lib bormoqda.

Ta'lim jarayonining rivojlantiruvchi texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etilishini ta'minlash hozirgi kunda dolzarb vazifalardan hisoblanadi. Endi o'qituvchi faqat bilim berish va amaliy ko'nikmani shakllantirish bilan chegaralanmasdan o'quvchilarni mustaqil bilim olish, izlanish va qarorlar qabul

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim, tarbiya, pedagog, pedagogik texnologiya, bilim, ko'nikma, malaka, nazariya, ma'anaviyat, madaniyat, psixologik tarbiya, differensiyalashgan yondashuv.

Ta'lim jarayonini rivojlantiruvchi texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etish pedagogdan katta mahorat talab etadi. Rivojlantiruvchi texnologiyalar o'qituvchidan nafaqat o'quvchilarga bilim berish, ularda amaliy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishni, balki ularning shaxsini rivojlantirishni talab etadi. Bunda ta'lim beruvchi bilan ta'lim oluvchining bir-biriga o'zaro ishonch, hamkorligi va jonli muloqoti orqali erishiladi. Rivojlantiruvchi texnologiyalar ta'lim jarayonida boshqacha yondashuvni talab qiladi. O'qituvchi o'quvchiga va fanga nisbatan o'zining munosabatini o'zgarishga to'g'ri keladi.

Pedagog ta'lim oluvchi shaxsini hurmat qilishi, muloqot qilishning buyruqbozlik usulidan voz kechib, uni rag'batlantirishi, bajargan ishlarining foydali ekanini tasdiqlashi zarur. Maqsad o'quvchida avvaldan belgilangan xususiyatlarni shakllantirish emas, balki o'z-o'zini anglashi, o'zligini namoyish etishi uchun imkon berishdir.

An'anaviy ta'lim majburiylikka, o'qitishni qattiqqo'llik asosida tashkil etishga asoslangan bo'lib, bunda ta'lim oluvchilar deyarli mustaqil faoliyat yuritishmaydi va ularning tashabbuslari bostiriladi. An'anaviy o'qitishda o'quvchining o'quv faoliyati ijodiy xarakterga ega bo'lmaydi.

Biz kasbiy mahoratimizni, faqatgina ta'lim oluvchilarning bilimlari va mahoratlarini nazorat lim, ko'nikma va malaka bilish va qo'llashda yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan qiyinchiliklarni o'z vaqtida bartaraf etishga malakali harakatlarimiz bilan yordam berishimiz uchun, ularning faoliyatini tashxis qilishga yo'naltirishimiz kerak.

Rivojlantiruvchi texnologiyalar, o'z mohiyatiga ko'ra, ta'lim jarayonining barcha

qatnashchilarining to'laqonli rivojlanishini nazarda tutadi. Bu esa nafaqat ta'lim oluvchini tayyorgarligini, uni qobiliyatlari va imkoniyatlarini hisobga olgan holda o'qitishga differentsiyalashgan yondashuv, balki ta'lim oluvchining psixologik kasbiy va shaxsiy xususiyatlarini hamda qobiliyatlarini hisobga olish hamdir.

Rivojlantiruvchi texnologiyalar va uni amalga oshirishga Respublikamiz o'rta maxsus, kasb-hunar ta'limi mustaqil va erkin fikrlaydigan tashabbuskor, irodali kichik mutaxassislarni tayyorlashga katta e'tibor bermoqda. Shuningdek, kollejlarda ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonini yuqori darajada tashkil etish bilan qatorda o'quvchilarning qiziqishi, xohish-istagi va ehtiyojiga qarab kasb-hunarga tayyorlash asosiy maqsad etib qo'yilgan. Bugungi kunda kasb-hunar kollejlari kichik mutaxassislarni bozor iqtisodiyoti talab va ehtiyojlari asosida tayyorlash, tayyorlov yo'nalishlari bo'yicha davlat ta'lim standartlari talablari asosida o'quvchilarda bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarni shakllantirish, kelajakda mustaqil faoliyat yuritish qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish muxim ahamiyatga ega. Buning uchun kasb-hunar kollejlari ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonini tashkil qilish, boshqarish hamda sifatini nazorat qilishni yangicha yondashuv va zamonaviy usullar asosida ilmiy asoslangan mexanizmini yaratish talab etiladi.

Ta'lim texnologiyalarini ishlab chiqish paytida, biz rivojlantiruvchi ta'lim texnologiyalarni amalga oshiramiz.

Yuqoridagi chizmadan ko'rinib turibdiki, maqsadni amalga oshishi va kafolatlangan natijaga erishish, ham o'qituvchi, ham o'quvchining hamkorlikdagi faoliyati hamda ular qo'ygan maqsad, tanlangan mazmun, metod, shakl, vositaga, ya'ni texnologiyaga bog'liq. O'qituvchi va o'quvchi talabani maqsaddan natijaga erishishida qanday texnologiyani tanlashlari ular ixtiyorida, chunki har ikkala tamonning asosiy maqsadi aniq: natijaga erishishga qaratilgan, bunda o'quvchi –

talabalarning bilim saviyasi, guruh xarakteri, sharoitga qarab ishlatiladigan texnologiya tanlanadi, masalan, natijaga erishish uchun balkim kompyuter bilan ishlash lozimdir, balkim film, tarqatma material, chizma va plakatlar, turli adabiyotlar, axborot texnologiyasi kerak bo'ladi, bular o'qituvchi va o'quvchi-talabaga bog'liq.

Chunki, shaxs "Kadrlar tayyorlash Milliy dasturi" ning asosiy komponentlaridan hisoblanadi; shuningdek, kadrlar tayyorlash tizimining bosh sub'ekti va ob'ekti, ta'lim tizimining maqsadi, uning nufuzli sub'ekti bo'lib qolmoqda.

Bir qator tadqiqotlarda kasb-hunar ta'limida rivojlantiruvchi texnologiyalarni qo'llash imkoniyatlari va amalda tatbiq etilishi o'rganilgan.

Jumladan Q. Tolipov ishlarida zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar mohiyati va mazmuni ayniqsa modulli va muammoli o'qitish texnologiyalarni ta'lim jarayonida qo'llash imkoniyatlari yoritilgan.

I.A. Allayorov o'zining ilmiy ishida faol o'qitishning didaktik asoslarini ishlab chiqqan va ta'lim oluvchilarni faollashtirish ilmiy metodik tavsiyalari o'z aksini topgan.

N.N. Azizxodjaeva adabiyotlarda pedagogik texnologiyalar va ularni ta'lim jarayonidagi o'rni va ahamiyati yoritilgan.

B.L. Farberman asarlarida yangi pedagogik texnologiyalar va ularni ta'lim jarayonidagi o'rni va ahamiyati ochib berilgan.

Shuni ta'kidlash joizki, aksariyat tadqiqotlar va ilmiy pedagogik asarlarda, faqatgina o'qitish texnologiyasi nazariy jihatdan yoritilib berilgan.

Maxsus fanlar mazmunida ishlab chiqarish xususiyatlarining o'z aksini topishi, o'quvchi olgan nazariy bilimlarini amaliyotda qo'llay olish imkoniyati ta'minlashi kerak. Kasb-hunar kolleji o'quvchilari maxsus fanga tegishli faoliyat usullari bo'yicha yetarli bilim va ko'nikmalarga ega bo'lishlari lozim.

Xulosa

O'qituvchi va o'quvchi talabaning maqsaddan natijaga erishishida qanday texnologiyani tanlashlari ular ixtiyorida, chunki har ikkala tamonning asosiy maqsadi aniq: natijaga erishishga qaratilgan, bunda o'quvchi –talabalarning bilim saviyasi, guruh xarakteri, sharoitga qarab ishlatiladigan texnologiya tanlanadi, masalan, natijaga erishish uchun balkim kompyuter bilan ishlash lozimdir, balkim film, tarqatma material, chizma va plakatlar, turli adabiyotlar, axborot texnologiyasi kerak bo'ladi, bular o'qituvchi va o'quvchi-talabaga bog'liq. O'qituvchi tomonidan har bir darsni yaxlit xolatda ko'ra bilish va uni tasavvur etish uchun bo'lajak dars jarayonini loyihalashtirib olishi zarur. Bunda o'qituvchiga u tomonidan bo'lajak darsni texnologik xaritasini tuzib olishi katta ahamiyatga egadir. Chunki darsning texnologik xaritasi har bir mavzu, har bir dars uchun o'qitilayotgan predmet, fanning xususiyatidan, o'quvchi talabalarning imkoniyati va ehtiyojidan kelib chiqqan xolda tuziladi.

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JAMOAT JOYLARIDA MA'NAVIYATLI SHAXS ETIKETI, SO'ZLASHISH ODOBI.

Komilxo'jayev Zoxidjon Shuxrat o'g'li

Namangan davlat universiteti 3- bosqich talabasi, +998990173043

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada bugungi kunda jamoat joylarida ma'naviyati shaxs etikasida so'zlashish odobi haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: jamoat joylari, ma'naviyat, axloq, so'zlashish odobi

Etiketning qoidalari – odobga, odob – xushxulqqa, xushxulq - axloqiylikka olib boradi. Binobarin, axloq – jamiyat, zamon, ba'zan umumbashariy ahamiyatga ega, insoniyat tarixi uchun namuna bo'la oladigan ijobiy xatti-harakatlar yig'indisi, insoniy kamolot darajasini belgilovchi ma'naviy hodisa sifatida nafaqat shaxsni, balki butun bir jamiyat taraqqiyoti uchun muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Shu bois etiketni bugungi kunga kelib, texnika asri kishisining zamon talablariga javob beradigan madaniy-maishiy turmush tarzini go'zallashtirishga, o'zaro munosabatlar tizimini madaniylashtirishga xizmat qiluvchi fanning yangi tarmog'i deyish mumkin.

Donishmandlarning “Yuziga boqma, so'ziga boq”, degan hikmatlari ayni haqiqatdir. Til – inson tafakkuri mahsuli. U inson madaniyati fikriy go'zalligini yaxshi, ibratli, havas qilsa arziydigan fazilatlarini yuzaga chiqaruvchi vositadir. Muomala esa insonlarni bir-biriga bog'lovchi, yaqinlashtiruvchi, katta-kichik xayrli ishlarga undovchi fazilatdir. Insonning go'zal hayot kechirishida, jamiyat orasida o'z o'rnini topa olishida, boshqalarning hurmat ehtiromiga erishishida muomalaning o'rni kattadir. Insonning shirinso'zligi kishining tarbiyalanganligidan guvohlik bersa, so'zga boyligi, chechanligi, ma'nodorligi uning o'qimishli, bilimdonligini ko'rsatadi. Go'zal muomala inson dilini qanchalik xushnud etsa, aksincha,, achchiq so'z, qo'pol muomala inson qalbini larzaga soladi. Shirin muomalada bo'lish ham katta san'at. Shirin so'z bilan kishining ishonchi va qalbini egallash mumkin. So'z, yuz va ko'z tilning ko'rki hisoblanadi. Insonning boshqa inson bilan muloqotiga qarab, uning axloqiga ham baho beriladi. So'z orqali insonlarning tafakkuri, fikri anglashiladi, muomala madaniyati orqali u kishining odobi, kelib chiqishi, nasl-u nasabi, ota-onasi va ustozining bergan ta'lim tarbiyasi namoyon bo'ladi. Insonning ichki dunyosi, shaxsi, aqli va his-tuyg'ulari uning tashqi qiyofasi – ko'zlari, chehrasi, shuningdek, qaddi-qomati va yurish-turishida to'la aks etadi. Insonning ichki dunyosi qanchalik mukammal bo'lsa, yurish-turishi ham shunchalik madaniyatli bo'ladi. Muomala madaniyatida so'z aqldan kuch, tildan ixtiyor oladi. Til shunday kuchga egaki, suyaksiz bo'lsa ham suyakni tebratadi. Muomala odobi boshqa kishilar qadr-qimmatini, izzatini joyiga qo'yishni, an'anaviy axloqiy-me'yoriy talablarini bajarishni taqozo etadi. Shuning barobarida, u insondagi yaxshi jihatlarni namoyon etishi, ko'zga ko'rsatishi bilan ham ajralib turadi. Uning eng yorqin, eng sermazmun va eng ifodali namoyon bo'lishi so'z, nutq vositasida ro'y beradi. So'zlash va tinglay bilish, suhbatlashish madaniyati muomalaning muhim jihatlari tashkil etadi. Shu bois muomala odobi o'zini, eng avvalo, shirinsuxanlik, kamsuqumlik, bosiqlik,

xushfe'llilik singari axloqiy me'yorlarda namoyon qiladi. Ayniqsa, bu axloqiy madaniyatda yaqqol ko'zga tashlanadi. Uni ko'proq namoyon qiladigan eng muhim unsurlaridan biri – muomala odobi. Bu borada mutasavvuf olimlarimizdan Imom G'azzoliy bir qancha o'rinli fikrlarni bildiradilar: "Hazrati Rasul alayhissalom aytibdurlar: "Haq subhonahu va taolo ochiq yuzlilarni do'st tutar". Va yana aytibdurlar: "Hech bir yaxshi amal yo'qki, mahfiratga sabab bo'lmoqg'a ochiq chehralik va shirinzabonliqdan ziyoda" Uning fikricha, shirinsuxanlik va bosiqlik odobli insonni odobsizdan ajratuvchi me'yordir. Zero, odobsizlik badxulqlikka, badxulqlik axloqsizlikka olib keladi. Yomon insonlarning yomonligi aynan muomaladan kelib chiqadi. Ya'ni yomonga yomonlik bilan qilingan muomala vaqtincha bo'lsa ham o'sha yomonning yo'lida yurishga chorlaydi. Donishmandlarning "Yuziga boqma, so'ziga boq", degan hikmatlari ayni haqiqatdir. Til – inson tafakkuri mahsuli. U inson madaniyatining fikriy go'zalligini yaxshi, ibratli, havas qilsa arziydigan fazilatlarini yuzaga chiqaruvchi vositadir. Muomala esa insonlarni bir-biriga bog'lovchi, yaqinlashtiruvchi, kattakichik xayrli ishlarga undovchi fazilatdir. Insonning go'zal hayot kechirishida, jamiyat orasida o'z o'rnini topa olishida, boshqalar tomonidan hurmat – ehtiromga erishuvida muomalaning o'rnini kattadir. Insonning shirinso'zligi kishining tarbiyalanganligidan guvohlik bersa, so'zga boyligi, chechanligi, ma'nodorligi uning ziyoliligi, bilimdonligini ko'rsatadi. Go'zal muomala inson dilini qanchalik xushnud etsa, aksincha,, achchiq so'z, qo'pol muomala inson qalbini larzaga soladi. "Muomala shaxslararo munosabatning shunday ko'rinishiki, uning yordamida odamlar bir-birlari bilan axloqiy, estetik, madaniy, siyosiy va ruhiy jihatdan aloqaga kirishadilar, ta'sir o'tkazadilar va ta'sirlanadilar". "Etiket" keng qamrovli tushuncha bo'lib, u ma'lum ma'noda, umumbashariy miqyosda qabul qilingan muomala qonun-qoidalarini o'z ichiga oladi. Ulardan bizga odat bo'lib qolgan ko'rishish etiketidir. Salom berish kundalik hayotimizda eng ko'p qo'llaniladigan odat bo'lib, xushmuomalalikni talab qiladi. Salomlashish kishilar o'rtasidagi o'zaro hurmat, muomala munosabatlarining avval boshi bo'lgani uchun uning bajarilishining ham alohida qoidalari bor. Salomlashganda aytiladigan so'zlarga "Assalom-u aleykum", "salomatmisiz", "omonmisiz", "yaxshimisiz", "salomat bo'ling" deyiladi. Bu so'zlarda, insonlarning bir-biriga hurmat-ehtiromi, xayrixohlik izhori bilan birga bu so'zlarda chuqur mazmun va mulohaza bor. Kundalik hayotimizda ishlatib turadigan "marhamat qiling", "baraka toping", "rahmat", "behad minnatdorman", "uzr", "avf etasiz", "kechiring" va shu kabi iboralar borki, ularning barchasi mulozamatni, insonlarga bo'lgan kamoli ehtiromni bildiradi. Shunga e'tibor berish kerakki, insonga qo'yiladigan talab bilan unga ko'rsatilayotgan iltifot bir-biri bilan bevosita bog'lanib ketganligidan ular orasiga chegara qo'yib bo'lmaydi. Masalan, birovning eshigini taqillatib ruxsat so'rab kirish boshqa insonni noqulay vaziyatga solib qo'yishning oldini oladi. Salomlashish insonning insonga bildirgan hurmati, odamlarning o'zaro muomala munosabatlarining boshlanishi, bir-biri bilan suhbatlashayotgan ikki dilning kalitidir. Salom berilganda sizga yoqimsiz qarab turgan inson ham alik oladi. Qo'l berib

ko‘rishayotgan vaqtda bir-birlarini qo‘llarini qattiq siqib, qo‘lini og‘ritib yoki qo‘lini uchinigina berib qo‘yish o‘ta odobsizlikka kiradi. Yoshlar o‘zidan katta odamlar bilan ko‘rishganlarida, albatta, ikki qo‘lini berib ko‘rishadilar. Ayniqsa, yosh bolalarning katta yoshdagilarga qo‘lini uzatib ko‘rishishlari ham odobsizlik sanaladi. Kim birinchi bo‘lib so‘rashishi lozim? Buning ham etiketda o‘ziga yarasha qoidalari mavjud: – yoshi kichiklar yoshi kattalarga; – erkaklar ayollarga; – xonaga kirgan inson u yerdagi barchaga umumiy; – zinadan chiqayotgan inson yuqori pog‘onadagilarga; – agar ikki oila uchrashib qolsa, ayollar birinchi bo‘lib so‘rashishlari, keyin esa erkaklar so‘rashishlari lozim; – qanday jamoat joylarida fikr bildirilishidan qat’i nazar, salomdan boshlash kerak; – yoshi va xizmat pog‘onasi teng insonlar uchrashib qolganlarida, birinchi bo‘lib tarbiyali inson so‘rashadi; – uyga kelgan mehmon eshikni ochgan insonga salom berishi, keyin uyning kattalari va boshqa mehmonlar bilan so‘rashishi kerak; – uy egalari hamma o‘tirganlar bilan bir xil so‘rashishlari lozim. Ulardan kimgadir alohida munosabat bilan so‘rashish odobsizlik hisoblanadi; – biror-bir insonga yuzlanishdan avval salomlashish lozim; – kechga qolib kelgan inson jamoatga birinchi bo‘lib salom beradi.

Uchta tushuncha zamon va makon tanlamaydi. Bular so‘zlash, tinglash va anglashdir. Odamzot yaralibdiki, o‘zaro munosabat jarayonida ana shu uch birlikka amal qilib kelinadi. Buning namoyon bo‘lishi har bir xalqning o‘z mentalitetiga mos va xos. O‘zaro munosabat, murojaat qilish jarayonidagi o‘zni tutish va fikr almashuvlar muomala madaniyati tushunchasida uyg‘unlashadi. Munosabat, murojaat, muloqot, munozara, mubohasa, muhokama, mulohaza singari tushunchalarning barchasi muayyan millatning tiynatiga mos bo‘lgan ziynatlar bo‘lib, u etik va estetik me‘yorlar, qoidalar bilan amalga oshiriladi.

Muloqot qisman monologik, asosan, dialogik, polilogik shaklda bo‘ladi. Boshqacha aytganda, ikki yoki undan ortiq kishilarning o‘zaro munosabatlarida reallashadi. Dunyo go‘zallik qonuniyatlariga binoan qurilarkan, demak, insonning xulqi va nutqi ham, ko‘rinishi va kiyinishi ham, munosabati va muloqoti ham go‘zal bo‘lishi maqsadga muvofiq. Xalqimizning “O‘zingga qarab kutarlar, so‘zingga qarab kuzatarlar” – degan o‘giti bejiz emas. “Til yarasi bitmas, tig‘ yarasi bitar” – deganida ham inson uchun zarur bo‘lgan muomala jarayoniga e‘tibor zaruriyatini sezish qiyin emas. Shaxs ma‘naviyatining uzviy bir bo‘lagi muomala madaniyati bo‘lsa, xulq-atvor, odob-axloq, nutqiy faoliyat tushunchalari uning zamiriga kiradi. Asrlar osha har bir xalqqa xos bo‘lgan, milliy-ma‘naviy qadriyatlar yuksak madaniyat ramziga aylangan urf-odatlar, yurish-turish, yashash tarzi barchasi kishi shaxsiyatida aks etishi tabiiy.

Ushbu risolada sharqona qarash, sharqona hayot falsafasi bilan bevosita bog‘liq bo‘lgan insonlararo munosabatlar me‘yori, shaxs ma‘naviyatining shaklanishida ularning o‘rni masalalariga e‘tibor qaratilgan.

Prezidentimiz ta‘biri bilan aytganda, “Yuksak bilimli, intellektual rivojlangan avlodni tarbiyalash – mamlakatni barqaror taraqqiy ettirish va modernizatsiya qilishning eng muhim sharti”

ekan, demak, ilm-fanga, ona vatanga munosabat o‘z-o‘zidan ma’naviyatli, barkamol inson tarbiyasida muhim va muqim o‘rin tutishi muqarrardir. Munosabat, shubhasizki, shaxsning muomala madaniyatidan kelib chiqadi. Bu esa barkamollik belgisi bo‘lgan ta’lim va tarbiyaga, ma’naviyat va ma’rifatga borib bog‘lanadi. Aqlan, ruhan va jismonan sog‘lom avlodgina yurtning porloq kelajagidir. Qushning parvozini qo‘sh qanotisiz tasavvur qilish mumkin bo‘lmaganidek, insonning iqboli va yurt istiqbolini ham ta’lim-tarbiya va ma’naviyat-ma’rifatsiz tushunish, idrok etish mushkul. Poetika, ritorika nazariyasini ilk tadqiqotchilaridan hisoblangan Aristotel san’at va madaniyat olamining paydo bo‘lishidagi ilk asos sifatida muomalani nazarda tutgani ham bejiz emas. Qolaversa, fransuz adibi Antuan Sent-Ekzyuperining “Bu dunyodagi birdan-bir haqiqiy ne’mat odamlarning bir-biri bilan muloqotidir”, -degan fikrida teran ma’no bor.

Ta’lim talabi nutq bilan, tarbiya talabi xulq bilan bog‘liq ekan, shaxs ma’naviyati, muomala madaniyati, muomala sirlari va odobi masalasi har qachongidan ham dolzarblik kasb etaveradi. Muomala “tarozisi”ning ikki pallasi bo‘lib, biri xulq, ikkinchisi nutqdir.

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LANGUAGE AND BODY LANGUAGE, LINGUISTICS

Qurbonova Muqaddam Axmedovna, Yusupova Dilshoda Raxmon qizi, Burxanovna Dilnoza
Ilhomjon qizi,
Kokand State Pedagogical Institute. Teacher

Annotation: As a social being human can't live in isolation and for exchanging of our ideas and views we get involved in intrapersonal communication. It is known to all that most important element of intra-personal communication is language without which a meaningful and clear exchange of views is impossible. Exchange of meaningful vocal tones for particular purpose through a language is commonly known as spoken language. We use written language also to express our views or ideas. while discussing over body language and language most of the people pay attention to verbal and written form of language but most of the people take help of another form of language i.e. body language. In this paper emphasis has been given on verbal, non verbal communication, body parts used in the communication, how status of people affects language and communication from childhood to end of life.

Key words: language and body language, linguistics, verbal, non verbal communication, body parts

Non-verbal communication is also used effectively to communicate one's emotions. Non-spoken communication which tells us something about the relationship between two or more people is known as Meta Communication. Language is affected through social status, personal status, economic status, political status both in verbal and non verbal. Way of presentation of urban people differs from rural people. In both form of communication body parts are used according to need. In this paper emphasis has been given on verbal, non verbal communication, body parts used in the communication, how status of people affects language and communication from childhood to end of life.

Linguistics is the scientific study of language. It encompasses the analysis of every aspect of language, as well as the methods for studying and modeling them. The traditional areas of linguistic analysis include phonetics, phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics, and pragmatics: Areas of linguistics, Conversation analysis, Forensic phonetics and linguistics, Historical and anthropological linguistics, Phonetics and phonology, Sociolinguistics, Syntax and semantics. Linguists study language structure at several theoretical levels that range in size from tiny units of speech sounds to the context of an entire conversation. ... The smallest units of language are studied in the field of phonetics, which concerns itself with the individual sounds produced while speaking.

"Body actions are linguistic, rather than just a sideshow or add-on to the meaning produced in words." Human gesturing is known in linguistics as "co-speech behaviour." It includes manual gestures, head movements, shoulder shrugs, postural shifts, eye gaze and brow movements linked to certain verbal expressions

The many different types of nonverbal communication or body language include:

Facial expressions. The human face is extremely expressive, able to convey countless emotions without saying a word: Body movement and posture, Gestures, Eye contact, Touch, Space, Voice, A shrug of the shoulders, a raised eyebrow or two hands weighing alternatives.

Physical gestures may be intrinsically linked to human expression, but linguistics hasn't always recognized their vital role in producing meaning, seeing them as mere adornments to speech.

Linguist Jennifer Hinnell is determined to change that, and she's off to a brilliant start. Her PhD thesis on the topic won this year's Governor General's Gold Medal, the University of Alberta's top doctoral award.

Beyond a better understanding of how gesturing contributes to human conversation, her research has applications in fields from neuroscience to designing animated avatars in video games.

The gist of her argument is that language is "inherently embodied."

"When people are talking face to face, you can't strip the body out of the linguistic signal," she said. "Body actions are linguistic, rather than just a sideshow or add-on to the meaning produced in words."

Human gesturing is known in linguistics as "co-speech behaviour." It includes manual gestures, head movements, shoulder shrugs, postural shifts, eye gaze and brow movements linked to certain verbal expressions.

When people converse, they really can't help getting their body involved, she said, however slightly, and in ways that sometimes "almost fly under the radar."

An obvious example is a person weighing two options. They might lift one hand, palm out, then the other, but they might just tilt their head slightly from side to side, as if expressing "the internal experience of the contrast," said Hinnell.

To do her research, Hinnell turned to the Red Hen Lab, a huge database of American broadcast television clips-mostly from news programming and talk shows. All of the clips are closed-captioned, which made machine searching for phrases and expressions far easier, she said.

She explained that because our gesturing to some extent implies our experience of physical forces, it can likely be understood across cultures, regardless of the verbal language spoken.

"There is a fair amount that's universal, because we all live in a physical embodied world in these human bodies. "When people express an ongoing event, for example, they draw a big timeline in front of them with their hands, a cyclical movement to show it's repeated over time, or an abrupt gesture when it ends suddenly."

The word Language has been derived from Latin lingua, "language, tongue", via Old French. This metaphoric relation between language and the tongue exists in many languages and testifies to the historical prominence of spoken languages. (www.wikipedia.com). When used as a general

concept, "language" refers to the cognitive faculty that enables humans to learn and use systems of complex communication. Language is specifically a quality of human capacity for acquiring and using complex systems of communication or to a specific instance of such a system of complex communication. As a system of symbolic communication, language is traditionally seen as consisting of three parts: signs, meanings and a code connecting signs with their meanings. Signs can be composed of sounds, gestures, letters or symbols, depending on whether the language is spoken, signed or written and they can be combined into complex signs such as words and phrases. When used in communication a sign is encoded and transmitted by a sender through a channel to a receiver who decodes it a signal. "In making a speech one must study three points: first, the means of producing persuasion; second, the language; third the proper arrangement of the various parts of the speech." (Aristotle). One definition sees language primarily as the mental faculty that allows humans to undertake linguistic behavior to learn languages and produce and understand utterances. This definition stresses the universality of language to all humans and the biological basis of the human capacity for language as a unique development of the human brain. Many philosophers have tried to define language according to their views but whatever the definition, prime motto of language is to establish communication among two or more person for a particular purpose. Body language is considered to be an outward reflection of person posses' emotional condition. Body Language:- Apart from verbal communication, non-verbal communication is also used effectively to communicate one's ideas and intentions i.e. body language. Body language is a form of non-verbal communication, which consists of body posture, gestures, facial expressions and eye movements. Humans send and interpret such signals almost entirely subconsciously. Body language may provide clues as to the attitude or state of mind of a person. For example, it may indicate aggression, attentiveness, boredom, relaxed state, pleasure, amusement, and intoxication, among many other cues. According to Aric Watson " Body Language is a such science which put effect on each and every part of our life. Factually Body Language is a such system through which a person, not only can have knowledge of other people by seeing movements of one's body but also can develop himself accordingly and can make himself a successful person. Body Language is a such art through which a person can achieve new goal of popularity." (Body Language: 2010). Understanding body language Physical expressions are integral part of non verbal communication. Physical expressions like waving, pointing, touching and slouching are all forms of nonverbal communication. Humans move their bodies when communicating because, as research has shown, it helps "ease the mental effort when communication is difficult.". Physical expressions reveal many things about the person using them. For example, gestures can emphasize a point or relay a message, posture can reveal boredom or great interest and touch can convey encouragement or caution. The technique of "reading" people is used frequently to understood a people as a whole. For example, the idea of mirroring body language to put people at

ease is commonly used in interviews. Mirroring the body language of someone else indicates that they are understood. It is important to note that while some indicators of emotion are largely universal. In the 1990s Ekman expanded his list of basic emotions, including a range of positive and negative emotions not all of which are encoded in facial muscles.

Body Language Communicates When Words Can't:- It has been seen in most of the people that many time they are not able to communicate the exact message what actually they want through their words in a personal interaction. This type of situation occurs when a person is highly emotional, may be with affection or love or anger. Mare a smile can show your feeling of joy and anger in eyes can show pains in mind. A person's sense of pride in his or her performance swells almost to bursting, so they turn to each other and make eye contact. One of them might smile, squeeze each other's hands, or they can lean together. These are V. P. Singh ~ 167 ~ all ways of non-verbal communication something important in a way that's far more effective and meaningful than using plain old words.

Language and body language is affected by social, economic etc status. Social Status and living standard affects both verbal and non verbal communication. Way of using language and body language by a rural person differs from a person of urban area. Way of rising hands, walking and movement of body all are affected by this factor. It has been observed by the writer that important reason behind such behavior may be inferior complex in rural person and superiority complex in an urban person. Economic status particularly in India is taken as very important factor regarding use of language and body language. Language and body language of economically sound people remains authoritative and orderative while language and body language of economically unsound person give indication of request. Some tips for personality relationship development (i) Have good command over language. (ii) Quote idioms and phrase and sayings of people during deliberation of lecture. (iii) Use grammatically right form of language with good sounding words. V. P. Singh ~ 170 ~ (iv) Keep smiling face with pleasing look. (v) Normally don't appear to anybody with crossed arms and legs. (vi) Be always good listener because until unless a person will not listen others it will not be possible to understood what exactly person wants to communicate. Only good listeners are good responder by their vocal or body language. (vii) Try to avoid immediate reaction, as our system of body sometimes takes good time to take things exactly due to various moods situationally or biologically. (viii) Keep adequate distant during interaction as people dislike entry of other person in their personal space. Importance of personal spaces plays very immense role family relation (husband-wife relationship) also. Every person needs personal space to think and to be comfortable. It has been observed during any problem male partner want silence or loneliness to think over solution of particular problem while female partner give instant reaction by nodding over the matter and wants mostly discussion over that. It gives feeling of interference, into personal space to male partner, which irritates him and this becomes starting point of quarrel among them. Finally it leads to breaking of relationship. Hence

keep adequate distance while communicating. (ix) May social, economic, political statuses vary but one must not forget that knowledge is much more than these differences. So, one must try to acquire good and proper knowledge for good personality as well as communication. A wealthy person may impress initially due to his money but in long term he will be less successful socially than a knowledgeable and learned person.

This is how we conclude that if Language is a means of our interaction in society than, no doubt Body language is a mirror of personality development. It can read mentality of other people and a person can easily make himself according to others mentality and take decision for good planning in a successful and effecting manner. Body language speaks about the mental attitude and the physical fitness as well as physical ability of the person. It gives better understanding of people and their intention. It develops a better rapport than a long conversation or debate. Body language reading is of immense importance for adaptive social behavior and non-verbal communication. This ability constitutes a central component of social competence. Healthy perceivers are able to infer emotions and dispositions of others represented by point-light body movements that minimize availability of other cues. Perceivers can reliably judge emotional content of people represented by a few movements. Visual sensitivity to camouflaged point-light human locomotion is modulated by the emotional content of gait with the highest sensitivity to angry walking. Observers can discriminate between deceptive and true intentions conveyed by body motion, and true information is precisely detected despite misleading endeavors. Hence, it is true one should have good knowledge of language for communication and good sense of body language for better understanding among people as well as in society.

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APPLIED LINGUISTICS AND THE INTERNATIONAL ASSOCIATION

Nishonova Shaxnoza¹, Maxsudova Umida²
^{1,2} Kokand State Pedagogical Institute, lecturer

Annotation: In this paper, Applied linguistics is an interdisciplinary field which identifies, investigates, and offers solutions to language-related real-life problems. Some of the academic fields related to applied linguistics are education, psychology, communication research, anthropology, and sociology, are mentioned.

Key words: linguistics, scientific study, applied linguistics and the international association

Though the term "applied linguistics" has traditionally been associated with the scientific study of such areas as TESOL, TEFL, TESL, language teaching and learning, applied linguists do a variety of things: The basic idea is, as the definition implies, to contribute to the real-world issues. Some of the questions that applied linguists ask include:

- How can languages best be learnt and taught?
- What social factors affect language learning?
- How can technology be used to contribute to the effectiveness of language teaching/learning?
- What are the related problems associated with language disorders? How can these be prevented?

Though Applied Linguistics. Organization is not any more under construction, we still have a lot to do! We are open to any suggestions that could help make this site a big contribution to the field.

Applied linguistics is an interdisciplinary field. Major branches of applied linguistics include bilingualism and multilingualism, conversation analysis, contrastive linguistics, sign linguistics, language assessment, literacies, discourse analysis, language pedagogy, second language acquisition, language planning and policy, interlinguistics, stylistics, language teacher education, pragmatics, forensic linguistics and translation.

The tradition of applied linguistics established itself in part as a response to the narrowing of focus in linguistics with the advent in the late 1950s of generative linguistics, and has always maintained a socially-accountable role, demonstrated by its central interest in language problems.[1]

Although the field of applied linguistics started from Europe and the United States, the field rapidly flourished in the international context.

Applied linguistics first concerned itself with principles and practices on the basis of linguistics. In the early days, applied linguistics was thought as "linguistics-applied" at least from the outside of the field. In the 1960s, however, applied linguistics was expanded to include language assessment, language policy, and second language acquisition. As early as the 1970s, applied linguistics became a problem-driven field rather than theoretical linguistics, including the solution of

language-related problems in the real world. By the 1990s, applied linguistics had broadened including critical studies and multilingualism. Research in applied linguistics was shifted to "the theoretical and empirical investigation of real world problems in which language is a central issue." [2]

In the United States, applied linguistics also began narrowly as the application of insights from structural linguistics—first to the teaching of English in schools and subsequently to second and foreign language teaching. The linguistics applied approach to language teaching was promulgated most strenuously by Leonard Bloomfield, who developed the foundation for the Army Specialized Training Program, and by Charles C. Fries, who established the English Language Institute (ELI) at the University of Michigan in 1941. In 1946, Applied linguistics became a recognized field of studies in the aforementioned university. [3] In 1948, the Research Club at Michigan established *Language Learning: A Journal of Applied Linguistics*, the first journal to bear the term applied linguistics. In the late 1960s, applied linguistics began to establish its own identity as an interdisciplinary field of linguistics concerned with real-world language issues. The new identity was solidified by the creation of the American Association for Applied Linguistics in 1977.

The International Association of Applied Linguistics was founded in France in 1964, where it is better known as *Association Internationale de Linguistique Appliquée*, or AILA. AILA has affiliates in more than thirty countries

Australian applied linguistics took as its target the applied linguistics of mother tongue teaching and teaching English to immigrants. The Australia tradition shows a strong influence of continental Europe and of the US, rather than of Britain. [5] Applied Linguistics Association of Australia (ALAA) was established at a national congress of applied linguists held in August 1976. [6] ALAA holds a joint annual conference in collaboration with the Association for Applied Linguistics in New Zealand (ALANZ).

The British Association for Applied Linguistics (BAAL) was established in 1967. Its mission is "the advancement of education by fostering and promoting, by any lawful charitable means, the study of language use, language acquisition and language teaching and the fostering of interdisciplinary collaboration in this study [...]". [11] BAAL hosts an annual conference, as well as many additional smaller conferences and events organised by its Special Interest Groups (SIGs).

Applied Linguistics Today

Over the intervening years, the foci of attention have continued to broaden. Today the governing board of AILA describes applied linguistics 'as a means to help solve specific problems in society...applied linguistics focuses on the numerous and complex areas in society in which language plays a role.' * There appears to be consensus that the goal is to apply the findings and the techniques from research in linguistics and related disciplines to solve practical problems. To an observer, the most notable change in applied linguistics has been its rapid growth as an interdisciplinary field. In

addition to foreign language teaching and machine translation, a partial sampling of issues considered central to the field of applied linguistics today includes topics such as language for special purposes (e.g. language and communication problems related to aviation, language disorders, law, medicine, science), language policy and planning, and language and literacy issues. For example, following the adoption of English as the working language for all international flight communication by the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), some applied linguists concerned themselves with understanding the kinds of linguistic problems that occur when pilots or flight engineers from varying backgrounds communicate using a nonnative language and how to better train them to communicate in English more effectively.

Some applied linguists are concerned with helping planners and legislators in countries develop and implement a language policy (e.g. planners are working in South Africa to specify and to further develop roles in education and government not only for English and Afrikaans but also for the other nine indigenous languages) or in helping groups develop scripts, materials, and literacy programs for previously unwritten languages (e.g. for many of the 850+ indigenous languages of Papua New Guinea).

Other applied linguists have been concerned with developing the most effective programs possible to help adult newcomers to the United States or other countries, many of whom have limited if any prior education, develop literacy in the languages which they will need for survival and for occupational purposes. Other topics currently of concern to applied linguists are the broad issue of the optimal role of the mother tongue in the education of culturally and linguistically diverse students, the language of persuasion and politics, developing effective tools and programs for interpretation and translation, and language testing and evaluation.

In the United Kingdom, the first school of applied linguistics is thought to have opened in 1957 at the University of Edinburgh with Ian Catford as Head. In the United States, a nonprofit educational organization, the Center for Applied Linguistics (CAL), was founded in 1959 with Charles Ferguson as its first Director. CAL's mission remains to 'promote the study of language and to assist people in achieving their educational, occupational, and social goals through more effective communication'. The organization carries out its mission by collecting and disseminating information through various clearinghouses that it operates, by conducting practical research, by developing practical materials and training individuals such as teachers, administrators, or other human resource specialists to use these to reduce the barriers that limited language proficiency can pose for culturally and linguistically diverse individuals as they seek full and effective participation in educational or occupational opportunities.

Organizations

In addition to the international organization AILA, there are also major national associations of

applied linguists such as the American Association for Applied Linguistics (AAAL) and the British Association for Applied Linguistics (BAAL). The work of applied linguists is frequently presented or described in publications such as the journal Applied Linguistics (Oxford University Press) and the Annual Review of Applied Linguistics (Cambridge University Press).

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ОБУЧЕНИЕ НАРОДНЫМ ПРОМЫСЛАМ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫМ ЦЕННОСТЯМ В ДОШКОЛЬНЫХ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЯХ РАЗВИТИЯ

Ҳасанова Диловар Жураевна

Педагог первой группы подготовки к школе 11-го ОДО города Термеза

Аннотация: Обучение народным ремеслам и национальным ценностям в дошкольных учреждениях и влияние национальных традиций на их воспитание, развитие ребенка.

Ключевые слова: нравственное воспитание, педагогический, психологический, эстетический.

Как указано в статье 3 Закона Республики Узбекистан «О дошкольном образовании и воспитании», принятого Законодательной палатой 22 октября 2019 года и одобренного Сенатом 14 декабря 2019 года. Дошкольное образование и воспитание - это тип непрерывного образования, направленный на обучение и воспитание детей, их интеллектуальное, духовное, моральное, этическое, эстетическое и физическое образование, а также подготовку детей к общему среднему образованию. Дошкольное образование - это основа образования. Именно поэтому Республика Узбекистан гарантирует образование каждому дошкольнику. В наше время детям дошкольного возраста уделяется много внимания. Как было сказано выше, дошкольное образование - это основа нашего образования, а дошкольники - основа нашего будущего.

Поэтому воспитание и образование подрастающего поколения начинается с дошкольного образования, которое является основным звеном в системе государственного образования. Воспитание подрастающего поколения в соответствии с духовными качествами, раскрывающими их отношение к обществу, работе и себе - сложный процесс, требующий глубокого знания педагогических и психологических основ нравственного воспитания. Только осознанное приобретение нравственных знаний может помочь детям понять, что хорошо, а что плохо в поведении окружающих. Древнегреческие философы Платон и Арасу утверждали, что воспитание детей должно быть на усмотрение общества и что вся необходимая работа в процессе воспитания должна выполняться государством. Они хотели доказать, что воспитание детей отвечает интересам общества. Задача и содержание нравственного воспитания дошкольников - воспитать и развить духовный мир ребенка, его сознание, нравственные чувства, личностные качества, реализовать содержание нравственного воспитания.

Задачи нравственного воспитания дошкольников:

1. Воспитание у детей нравственного восприятия и поведения.
2. Воспитывайте культуру поведения и позитивное отношение.
3. Воспитание нравственных чувств у детей.
4. Устранение отрицательных качеств в поведении.

Нравственное воспитание в дошкольных учреждениях осуществляется разными способами. Прежде всего, дети знакомятся с работой взрослых посредством различных занятий, как в классе, так и вне его. Различные праздники, светские мероприятия, детская литература, музыка, игровые материалы, средства массовой информации - телевидение, радио и т. Д. - имеют большое влияние на нравственное воспитание детей. Необходимо расширить нравственные переживания детей, выявить моральные причины поведения. Во время беседы детям предоставляется возможность высказать свое мнение. Затем они стараются совершать каждое действие осознанно, в рамках норм и правил морали. Чтение художественной литературы, просмотр произведений искусства и прикладного искусства, прослушивание музыки и пение прививают детям эстетическое чутье, а также воспитывают правила и нормы морали.

В нынешний период растущее осознание «национальной идентичности» требует дальнейшего развития национальных чувств, которые формируются у подрастающего

поколения, особенно в дошкольном образовании. Дошкольное образование требует внедрения гуманного подхода к личному воспитанию, основанного на богатом духовном и интеллектуальном наследии народа и общечеловеческих ценностях. Он включает в себя патриотизм, основанный на национальной гордости, национальных ценностях, солидарности и солидарности. Чем сильнее у подрастающего поколения любовь и гордость за Родину, тем сильнее любовь и уважение к Родине, тем сильнее история, национальные ценности, родной язык, культура, национальные традиции каждого человека. стабильный, если в совершенстве знает свои обычаи и традиции, глубоко понимает судьбу и будущее нации. В настоящее время проблема духовности является одним из основных направлений в укреплении независимости, формировании духовности личности в уверенном стремлении к независимости. Только человек со зрелой культурой обретает идеологию независимости и идет в будущее на основе согласия и братства. Национальный язык и национальная культура, национальное сознание, национальное самосознание, национальное чувство, национальная гордость и гордость играют важную роль в восстановлении и развитии нашей духовности. Понимание нации как объекта и субъекта национальных ценностей, научный анализ связанной с ней системы национальных ценностей позволяет нации рассматривать себя как социальную ценность. Это позволяет анализировать проявление национальных ценностей, движение от прошлого к будущему в процессе исторического развития. Национальные ценности: - формируются в этническом пространстве, обеспечивающем естественное, историческое и социальное единство людей, проявляются в самых разных формах, оказывают уникальное влияние на сознание и образ жизни людей:

- отражается в человеческих отношениях, социальной деятельности и является духовной основой этих взглядов, действий, целей, потребностей и стремлений;

- могут возникнуть в результате в материальной, духовной, экономической, политической и других сферах, иметь особое значение как необходимость для людей и могут принести им пользу;

- В процессе общественного развития, изменений и улучшений, красочные аспекты передаются из поколения в поколение, передаются по наследству.

Система ценностей, являющаяся выражением национальных ценностей и их взаимосвязанности, сама нация движется из прошлого в будущее через череду историй, эпох, различных социальных и политических процессов. Эти ценности больше связаны с этническими особенностями и этническим пространством нации. И социальное развитие людей будет и впредь неразрывно связано с развитием их национальных и этнических ценностей. По мере того, как каждая нация или нация развивает свой собственный разнообразный набор ценностей, они развивают универсальные ценности и формируют его

грани.

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ADVANTAGE OF SEED GERMINATION IN THE CONDITIONS OF UZBEKISTAN

PhD R.X.Muradov

Student B. B. Gulomov

Annotation: When wheat is planted in pots, a flat sprout emerges due to the increase in the area of the field exposed to sunlight, the greater accumulation of heat in the top layer of soil, and the higher its temperature relative to flat ground. Good development and high yields of germinated wheat seedlings are achieved.

Key words: Agrotechnical, seed, soil, wheat, germination, norm, planting, harvesting.

It is known that in the 440-485 thousand hectares of cotton fields in the Republic, cotton is harvested and sown. The practice of obtaining Pushta is widely used mainly in Andijan and Namangan, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya Regions [1, 2; 12-14-b.].

Because, planting out of the bush for certain soil-climatic conditions is more effective than planting on flat ground, which makes it possible for the seeds to germinate sooner, develop better and harvest.

Currently, all agrotadbirs belonging to the technology of planting in Pushta are introduced in accordance with the "standard technological cards for 2016-2020 years for the care and cultivation of agricultural crops" approved by the Ministry of Industry [1, 2, 3; 37-44-b.].

We can see that the analysis has been improving the processes of processing the lands of farmers in the territory of the Republic in recent years, especially in the scientific-research work carried out on the creation of technology and technical means for planting crops in the Bush, as well as their introduction into agricultural production. For example, the authors of these publications mentioned the following points on the advantage of the technology of cultivation in cotton [1; 67-b., 2, 3, 4, 5; 20-21-the b., 6; 64-67-b., 7; 12-14-b., 8; 12-20-b., 9; 34-36-b., 10]:

- field in the planting of seedlings in relation to the methods used an increase in the surface is achieved;
- because of the increased surface on which the crop is planted, the degree of exposure of heat to the soil is achieved in the spring to more than 2,20;
- the opportunity to plant more grain seeds into the bushy area;
- it is possible to form and irrigate watering ditches in the formation of pus;
- the probability of accumulation of excess rainwater on the field surface is reduced, through irrigation ditches it is easier to extract excess water, as a result of which the diseased of the planted seeds, the probability of hardening of the fields is reduced;
- reduced seed grain crops to be wasted;
- the yield of grain crops is reached 4,7-5,9 centners per hectare higher than the current methods;
- on account of the correct exposure of sunlight in the pink areas, a favorable environment is created for the early germination of seeds under the soil and good heating of the plant root system.

This means that all of the above factors also have their impact on the grain crop to be grown and it is necessary to carry out scientific research in this area.

This means that, based on the above, planting autumn bug'doy seeds in the open field to the Bush, placing the seeds in the unit of the surface of a certain area at a specified norm, ensuring their uniformity on the surface of the sown area and to the specified depth can be carried out on the basis of the following advantages:

- when plucked, the surface of the field increases;
- the number of rows fertilized on the surface of the field increases;
- effective use of water increases;

In conclusion, when sown in the Bush, the increase in the volume of the layer of loose soil, in which their roots develop, an increase in the surface of the field in which sunlight falls, a greater accumulation of heat in the upper layer of the soil and its temperature is higher than in the flat ground, a uniform flourishing is achieved. Good development and high yield cultivation of sprouted oats is achieved.

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RELATIONS BETWEEN KHOREZM AND IRAN, TRADE RELATIONS AND POLITICAL RELATIONS

Matkarimov Khamidbek Olimboyevich¹, Kuzieva Nodira O'ktamboy kizi²

¹ UrSU History teacher, [Tel:+998919971331](tel:+998919971331)

² History direction 2nd year student, E-mail: nadiraoktamavnaa@gmail.com

Annotation: This article discusses diplomatic relations between the Khiva Khanate and Iran, the Iranian embassy missions visiting the Khiva Khanate and Iran's interest in foreign relations and trade with the Khiva Khanate. Keywords: Khorezm, Khiva, Iran, Muhammad Rahiman, Olloqulino, Isfahan, trade relations, diplomatic relations.

Keywords: Khiva Khanate, Iran, political relations, diplomacy, foreign policy, Muhammad Rahimkhan, Allakulikhan, Urgench, war.

There are reports that Khorezm has long had trade relations with Eastern countries. From the X century Khorezm merchants Near and Middle East Trade relations between Iran and Khorezm have been developing since the Middle Ages, which later led to the establishment of diplomatic relations between the two countries. In the Middle Ages from Iran to Khorezm there were "kazerun" fabrics, minna-type tiles, ceramics and bustrav pottery, which can be found in the sources of medieval history. perfumes, carpets, agricultural products. [1] Eleventh-century data show that Khorezm-Iran relations continued in the traditional way. Jenkenson, writing about the Urgench markets, noted that the main goods sold in the markets here were brought from Bukhara or Iran. As much as the skill of experienced ambassadors played an important role in interdepartmental agreements, so did the gifts and greetings given. In his lifetime, the exchange of gifts and presents between rulers was a trade-off. can be considered as a type. In this way, both countries not only promoted their products and the high quality of the link, but also served to warm diplomatic relations. We can see a similar situation between Khiva and Iran. For example, in Abulgazy Bahodirkhan's "Shajarayi Turk", among the royal gifts sent by the Iranian king Tahmosib on the occasion of his marriage to Ilya, the khan of Khiva, Bochrawon, We can cite lacquered silver silk saab. [2] It is evident that gifts were important in the middle of the rulers. Represents the relationship that exists. In addition, the exchange of gifts between the rulers also affected trade and diplomatic relations. During this period, when we talk about trade relations between the Khiva Khanate and Iran, trade between the two countries was important and beneficial for the citizens, traders of any state. It is said that Central Asian merchants brought silk fabrics from Iran, along with hinc goods such as pepper and ginger, from Isfahan. Trade relations between Khorezm and Iran, which date back to ancient times, flourished during the Khiva Khanate. however, there were a number of political, economic, and social tensions and problems between Khiva and Iran.

Mirza Alim Mahdum Haji's "History of Turkestan" assesses Muhammad Rahimkhan I's relations with neighboring countries, saying that "... there were always conflicts with the kings of Iran and he sent troops to the sides of Astrabad." [3] Muhammad Rahimkhan ended the feudal

disintegration of the Khiva khanate and established a centralized state in the lands of Khorezm. Rahimkhan waged periodic wars against Bukhara to occupy Karakol and Chorjoi, as well as Bukhara lands in the upper reaches of the Amu Darya, and against Iran to occupy Iranian lands in the southwestern part of the Merv. According to reports, as early as 1812, Muhammad Rahim started a war against Iran. Khiva's troops invaded villages on the Iranian border. There will also be action against Rahim Khan. In addition, Kiva's troops were exhausted by the sufferings of the desert before they reached Iran. Tired Khiva's troops returned quickly, harvesting themselves until the winter so that they and their families would not go hungry in the winter. were trying to get. Noticing this, Rahim Khan, realizing that he could not fight against the Iranian military, ordered him to return to Khiva. If we pay attention to the sources of Khorezm, the attacks of the Khiva khans on the lands of Iran or the adjacent territories were based on a holy war waged in the name of religion, i.e. "gazat". If we look at the date on which these marches were held, it falls on Ramadan, which is a holy month for most Muslims.

Especially the fact that they went to war on Friday is a sign of victory over Iran and shows that this is a war for religion. In *Zubdat-ut-Tavorix*, Rahimkulikhan's march to Marv states that "on the eighth day of the holy month of Ramadan, on Friday, the hours would rise and the times would be exhausted." [4]

Khiva Khanate

In the work "History of Turkestan" there is information that the Khorezmians considered the Iranian population as "infidels and obligatory executions" and called them infidels. It is obvious that this belief was the reason for the Khiva khanate's conquests. The reason for Rahimkhan's return to Khiva was that the war between the two countries would end. But this peaceful relationship will not last long. In July 1827, Allakuikhan returned to Khiva with a large military force, capturing 6 cities and several villages in Iran and taking 2,000 captives in demand. He again marched on Iran in 1829 with 40,000 troops. According to the well-known orientalist N. Vasilovsky, the Khiva-Iran war was

the heaviest in the world. When the Khiva armed forces reached the Iranian border, they contracted plague and died. The khan was forced to return to Khiva with only 300 soldiers. However, they caused plague in Khiva, Bukhara, and throughout Central Asia, and many people died. [5] The khan of Khiva invaded Iran again in 1830, took 1,000 families captive and returned to Khiva. They were later assimilated into the indigenous population. Their descendants still live in the Khorezm oasis.

1837 In 1839, Iranian relations with the Khiva Khanate became very strained. In 1837, the khan of Khiva marched on Iran and intensified in the middle, but the war dragged on for a long time. In the early months of 1838, Khiva's troops attacked Iran. In July, a fierce battle broke out between the Iranian and Khiva armies in the vicinity of the city of Jamilagarh, and the Khiva army was forced to deknuly. In April 1833, Hirosa conducted a mascara with the Iranian deti ketibaa to improve economic and political relations between the state, and to tell the Iranian captives to return to their homeland. Uloguinhan sent his representatives to Iran. But since the Palace staff did not allow them to enter this diploma valamingo hug, they come to Hroci Higaytib. This case whitgan Olequeen 1819.yl yn cydia decides to start yang Yarish on tron. He gathered 10 soldiers and sent them from Ramongulva Mehtar Yaqubhey cachchilips. The Meskars marched on the Herat side, with the great death of the Guyads in 18424. Diplomatic relations were established with Eren and in the middle of the wound, and negotiations were held on the survival of the ickala state relations. But these negotiations did not yield any results. Thus, until the 50s and 60s of the twentieth century, transmutatieski holds colb, in some wars there is a urusar child between both creatures.

In conclusion, trade relations between the Khorezm oasis and Iran date back to ancient times and have developed over the centuries. As for the political situation of these states, each state tried to expand its territory during the period of its rise. This was done at the expense of neighboring territories. Of course, Iran also carried out looting raids on Khiva. The Khiva khans also invaded Iran and looted villages. The civilian population suffered from such diplomatic relations between the two countries. We know from history that rulers who believed in the power of their state carried out looting raids on the territory of the neighboring state. After the Khiva Khanate became a Russian protectorate, the khanate's diplomacy also passed into Russian hands. During this period, only trade relations with Iran will be carried out.

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DEVELOPMENT OF THE STRUCTURE OF THE INTELLIGENT DATA PROCESSING SYSTEM (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE INTEGRATED MANAGEMENT SYSTEM)

Zaynidinov Khakimjon Nasiridinovich Askaraliyev Odilbek Ulug‘bek o‘g‘li

¹ Tashkent university of information technologies named after Mukhammad al-Kwarizmi, head of department “Information technologies”, Professor, Doctor technical science.

² Tashkent university of information technologies named after Mukhammad al-Kwarizmi, assistant-teacher of department “Information technologies”. oasqaraliyev77@gmail.com

Technical solutions for the structure, functions and organization of data collection tools based on internal web systems and cloud source technology are proposed for the management structure. Strategic directions of software system development Intellectual analysis tasks: classification, training, forecasting A structure has been developed to increase the efficiency of large-scale electronic data processing. Intellectual information processing processes are analyzed in the example of integrated management systems, and final conclusions are drawn from existing solutions. It also offers an optimal structure for the internal web processing of data. The process of developing a visual representation of the process that coordinates the work of the expert system is described.

Key words: artificial intelligence, software systems, internet, algorithms, databases and knowledge, expert system, data processing.

Today, we can state that over the past decades there has been an intensive development of automated information systems (AIS), including in such areas as Internet network technologies, methods of storing and presenting knowledge, programming languages and tools, artificial intelligence methods, distributed and cloud algorithms. calculations, etc.

Scientific and technical advances in the field of artificial intelligence have influenced the formation of new and transformation of old classes of information systems - intelligent information systems, data mining systems, expert systems, decision support systems, etc. Unfortunately, all modern tools are in most cases scattered, solve particular subject problems or sharpened by one class of systems. At the same time, the level of their automation makes it possible to conclude that it is possible to develop a "super-system" that integrates all the most advanced tools (approaches, methods, models, algorithms, technologies) in the form of an intelligent repository of knowledge and automation of the process of information support for the adoption of management solutions.

The desire to increase the efficiency of using the information accumulated in electronic form (data banks, repositories, knowledge bases, etc.) through their integration and unification of storage formats and processing procedures has led to the development of Internet technologies [3] based on data mining methods (data mining).

The specificity of the IDPS leaves a significant imprint on the methodology and technology of its development. The technology for creating an IDPS has its own essential features and differs from the design and development process of other information and software systems. These differences are largely determined by the fact that IDPS are intelligent information systems (IIS) based on the ideas,

principles and methods of artificial intelligence (AI). Such systems require specialized approaches, methods and technologies for their implementation, which are significantly different from the classical methods of developing software systems. At the same time, the ever-growing interest in artificial intelligence contributes to the ever wider introduction and application of intelligent systems in various applied areas. The development of artificial intelligence systems (expert-oriented systems, data mining systems, translation, machine vision, etc.) is gradually reaching the industrial level, acquiring the features of an industry. This leads to the fact that such systems are beginning to meet the same requirements as for traditional software products.

The specificity of the IDPS is that the development and implementation of intelligent information systems is a rather long and laborious process [1], which has not yet been fully worked out and often requires new ideas and solutions, entails the use of extraordinary approaches, methods, technologies and tools. In addition, the implementation problem is also associated with the selection of suitable development tools, which is a separate complex task. Let us highlight the following fundamental features of the SPI that define it as a tool for expert decision support:

Ability to solve a wide range of problems in some non-formalized problem area.

– Ability to extract knowledge from data and represent it in the form of formalized knowledge models.

– Modeling the mechanisms of human intellectual activity.

– Use of knowledge about the subject area.

– Application of heuristic methods for solving problems.

– Ability to explain the resulting solution.

– High performance. Etc.

Cloud computing technology. A cloud is a computing complex based on virtual machines, capable of increasing or decreasing its characteristics with a minimum delay, on demand.

A remote computing service can be called cloud if it meets the rules formed in the American NITS (National Institute of Standards and Technology) (Standards Acceleration to Jumpstart Adoption of Cloud Computing (SAJACC) [<http://www.nist.gov>]). We divide services in the cloud into three basic categories:

- Infrastructure as a service - infrastructure as a service. The user is provided with an unlimited set of virtual machines, the configuration of which is configured by the user himself, and the user is also able to link them into a network and thus build his own virtual cluster of the configuration that he needs. At this level, the user has no control only over the hardware, everything else is subject to him.

- Platform as a service. The level where the user is abstracted from the level of virtual computers, networks, clusters. At this level, the user seems to have at his disposal a disk of infinite

size, a computer with infinite memory and an ultra-fast multicore processor. In fact, the platform is built in such a way that it organizes a cluster, which outwardly looks like a single machine.

- Software as a service. The user remotely uses any program. There is a cloud version of 1C, Photoshop, office programs. The user can only access the configuration of his account in the program and the configuration of the program itself in his session.

Data mining platform. The platform being developed can be classified as SaaS Business Intelligence (BI) or AaaS - Analysis as a Service.

The system also implies a client-side extension of functionality, and it is expected that the system will have part of the PaaS functionality.

The platform being developed has the following capabilities (SaaS BI):

– As a service, a workspace is provided (authentication and authorization, tools for uploading and editing files).

– Library of ready-made analysis subsystems and algorithms, including: classification and clustering, building rules and decision trees, neural networks, genetic algorithms, statistical algorithms, etc.

– Means for building an automatic collective solution based on algorithms.

– Tools for analyzing the effectiveness of training based on data.

– Visualization of analysis results.

Strategic plans include the ability to expand user functions to create and adjust individual sections of the Algorithm Library (PaaS), including:

– An editor for compiling new algorithms based on the metalanguage.

– Ability to build scenarios using analysis algorithms.

– Integration with business processes of users / customers (the server will automatically send specially configured data to the customer's server upon completion of the analysis or training, thereby organizing automatic data output to the customer's system).

– Working with the server via API (automatic data entry into the IDPS).

Strategic development plan. Intelligent data processing system (IDPS) is a software and hardware complex configured to use various recognition classes, languages and formats for presenting data and knowledge, an apparatus for synthesizing and analyzing model representations, as well as focused on providing services in the field of solving scientific and applied processing problems diverse data.

The complex integrates high-performance hardware (including powerful computing servers and extensive disk storage) and effective software (software) designed to solve a wide range of data mining tasks and allowing customization and expansion of the supported functions.

The system supports and implements the concept of "public cloud computing" and provides the

following categories of "cloud" services:

- Software as a service (Software as a Service, SaaS) - system users via the Internet get access to specialized software and using a web interface that functions in any modern browser, they can use it to solve their tasks, including resource-intensive ones;

- Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) - system users, if necessary, can lease computer infrastructure resources, for example, computer servers or data storage systems, for a long time, as well as attract intellectual resources provided by the team that support the operation to solve their problems and system development;

- Platform as a Service (PaaS) - based on the software and infrastructure provided by the system, users have the ability to supplement the functionality of the existing software, as well as develop, test and deploy their own web applications that other users can access within the framework SaaS.

Control system. A content management system is a software package that allows you to automate the process of managing both the site as a whole and the entities within the site: page layouts, data output templates, structure, content, users and access rights, as well as, if possible, providing additional services: lists mailings, statistics, search, means of interaction with users, etc.

Design solutions within the framework of the development of an intelligent repository of knowledge and automation of the information support process for making management decisions, together with data mining technologies, artificial intelligence methods, information presentation models, electronic databases in various subject areas, will serve as a tool to increase the efficiency of scientific, innovative and educational activities, and also in industry, economics, medicine, etc.

The practical implementation of the project allows it to be used as a self-adjusting, adaptive, open intelligent information system with integrated functions of an expert system and subsystems for data mining (knowledge extraction).

The proposed mathematical apparatus and the methodology for its use in the process of data analysis are a tool for scientific assessment and formal substantiation of the engineering decisions taken in various fields of forecasting, classification, and decision making. With this in mind, a system structure that helps the expert system coordinate the work is recommended as the optimal solution to the problem. This structure is implemented on the basis of appropriate resources, and the conceptual model of the operation of the mathematical apparatus and the analysis system is coordinated.

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T. QAYIPBERGANOVNING "MAMON BIY AFSONASI"DA SOMANTIZLIK
FRAZIOLOGIZMLARNING QÓLLANILISHI.
THE USE OF SOMAN PHRASEOLOGY IN T.KAIPBERGAN'S
"MAMANBIY LEGEND

Xojabaeva Altinoy Davlatboy qizi
Nukus davlat pedagogika instituti, Tu'rkiy tillar fakulteti, qaraqolpoq tili va adabiyoti
yo'nalishi 3-kurs talabasi

Xojabaeva Altinay Dáwletbay qizi
Nukus state pedagogical institute, Faculty of Turkish Languages, 3rd year
student of Karakalpak language and literature.

Annotatsiya. Tilda frazeologizmlarning qóllanilishi, somantizmlik frazeologizmlarning qóllanilish ózgachaligi, asarda somantizlik frazeologizmlarning qóllanilish ma'nolari haqida.

Kalit sózlar. Frazeologizm, somantizm, leksiko-semantik, stilistik qurol, emotsional-ekspressivlik ma'no.

Annotation. On the use of phraseology in the language, the peculiarities of the use of Somantism phraseology, the meaning of the use of somantism phraseology in the play.

Keywords. Phraseologism, Somantism, lexicol-semantc, cutilistic weapon, emotional-experssive meaning.

Turkiy tillar, shuning ichida qoraqalpoq tili sózlar tarkibida ózgacha gurux bólib taniladigan frazeologizmlarga ega juda ham boy til.

Haqiqatdan ham frazeologizmlar ózining obrazliligi, teran ma'nosi bilan kózga tushadigan har bir millat tilining ózgacha bir kórinishi hisoblanadi.

Frazeologizmlar badiy adabiyotlarda tasvirlashning leksiko-semantik, stilistik qurollarning biri sifatida kengiroq qóllaniladi. Frazeologizmlarning tarkibida qancha sóz bólishiga qaramasdan, ularning barchasi yigilib umumiy bir ma'noni anglatadi, emotsional-ekspressiv manoni bildiradi.

Masalan: Yuragi gash bólish- qórquv, kóz tashlash-qaramoq, quloq osish-tinglamoq, qóy oqzidan chóp olmaslik- yuvosh va boshqalar.[1:156]

SHuning bilan birga, frazeologizmlar har turli vaziyatlarda ham atamalarga bog'liq holda qóllaniladi. Masalan: inson azolariga bog'liq frazeologizmlar tilimizda kóplab uchraydi va linigivistikada somantizmlar degan atama bilan belgili hisoblanadi.

Qól sóziga bog'liq: qóli uzun, qólga olish, qóli kalta, qól yetmaslik, qól urush; kóz sóziga bog'liq: kózga tushmoq, kózi qamashmoq, kózni ochib yumguncha, kóz uchida, kózni ochmoq, kóziga chóp tiqmoq, oqiz sóziga bog'liq: oqzi ochiq, oqziga qaramoq, oqzi bilan yurmoq, oqziga osh solmoq, oqizga tushmoq va boshqalar.

T. Qayipberganovning qaysi asarlarini olsak ham, til birliklaridan chebarlik bilan foydalanganligini kóramiz. Yozuvchining "Qoraqalpoq dostoni" roman-trilogiyasining 1-kitobi "Mamon biy afsonasi"dagi inson azolariga bog'liq frazeologizmlar bilan tanishib chiqamiz.

Eshikdan kóz uchidagi yetim emanning ostida qózgalgan ipir-chipir kallalarni kórib shayx

gapin tóxtatdi. [2:23] Bunda, kóz uchuda - uzoqda degan manoni bildirib turibdi.

Hamma bir nafas lom-lumsiz qoldi. Badyoga ham qól urulmadi, pashsha vizzillasa eshitildi.

[2:24] Bunda, qól urulmadi - ovqat yeb boshlanmadi manosida.

SHusiz ham oǵzibirchiliksiz beylar xonga birinchi bajarganni shan bilib, buyruqni boshqasidan burun bajarishga shoshiladigan odati avvaldan bor.

[2:40] Bunda, oǵzibirchiliksiz - oǵzibirchiliksiz, gaplari bir joydan chiqmaydi degan manoda.

Degan bilan, yoshlarni sinash majlisigacha oǵzibirchilikli singari bólib yurgan beylarning Mamon saralab olgandan keyin tóyga qaramay ketkaniga hayron. [2:44] Bunda, aǵzibirchilikli-oǵzibirchilikli, totu manosida.

Ikkinchi qóriqchi gap tinglamay aravadagi nonga qol urib, pala-partish yeyapti. [2:53] Bunda, qol urib sózi - ovqat, nonni yeb boshlash manosida.

Tishimizdan chiqarishga óttiz ikki tishimiz tomoǵimizga ketadi deb qórqamiz. [2:56] Bundagi sóz, óttiz ikki tishimiz tomoǵimizga ketadi - qórquv, agar sirni oshkor etib aytib qóysang, sóz tishimizdan chiqsa, shu ayb uchun jazolanish manosida qóllanilgan.

U, shu ishonch bilan yomon xabar topib kelgan bolaga oǵzing yomon yerdan teshilgan deb chakkasiga bir tarsaki urib, ovozini óchirdi. [2:58] Bundagi, oǵzing yomon - órinsiz gapirish manosida. Bundagi oǵzi yomon - mafsiz odamlar nazarda tutulgan.

-Unday dema, Olloyor. Ikkalamizda ham gunoh yóq. Kim ikki yuzli bólsa, gunoh óshanda. [2:62] Bundagi, ikki yuzli sózi - sózin ikki gapirish manosida.

Irsqul beyning quloǵi tikrayib ketdi. [2:63]

Qaroqchilar hali uzoqlashib keta olmabdilar, kóz uchida changi kórinadi. [2:71]

-Tilim yetmaydi, aka. Lekin, Abilxayir xonning qishloǵi bilan bu qishloqning ónqir-chónqirin sezdim - dedi. [2:71]

Dard ichda qolsa, tilni boǵlashin hizir bildim, - dedi. [2:72]

Irsqul bey kóz ostidan payqadi, indamadi. [2:73]

Katta Qónǵirot uruǵining bir ustini Jandos boyning bu shumligin boshqa Qónǵirotlilar bildimi, yóqmi, u tógrisida óz quloqlarin tiymadi. [2:75]

-Kózini moy boskan...[2:78] Bundagi, kózini moy boskan - ózgarip, odam tanimas darajada degan manoda.

Qoraqalpoq xalqi qovirǵasidan yuragi kóringan mómin xalq. [2:81] Bundagi sózning manosi - qoraqalpoq xalqining qoniga singib ketgan baǵrikenglik va oqkónǵillilik fazilatlarini nazarda tutulgan.

Bugun "ikki el, egiz el" deydi. Ikki til ikki yuzli ushbu xonning ózida emasmi? [2:85] Bunda, ikki til, ikki yuzli sózi - órinsiz gapirish, ikki sózlash.

Hulosa qilib aytganda, frazeologizmlar kundalik turmushimiz bilan tiǵiz boǵliq. T.Qaypberganov óz asarlarida frazeologizmlardan shebarlik bilan foydalanganligini guvohi bóldik.

Frazeologizmlarning asarlardagi orni ahamiyatlidir.

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TA'LIM MENEJMENTIDA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARINING O'RNIIroda Mavlonberganova Ilhomjon qizi¹, Umida Mavlonberganova Ilhomjon qizi²^{1,2} Ajiniyoz nomidagi Nukus davlat pedagogika instituti

Annotsatsiya: O'zbekiston mustaqillikka erishganidan boshlab ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanib, xalqaro integratsiyaga qo'shilmoqda. Jamiyatimizning turli sohalarida rivojlanish ketayotganligi uchun axborotlar almashuvi masalasi tug'iladi. Hozirgi fan-texnikaning rivoji bir tomondan axborotlarni, ma'lumotlarni ko'paytirsa, ikkinchi tomondan, o'quvchilarda bilimlarga barqaror qiziqishning yo'qolishiga olib keladi. Axborot texnologiyalari va kommunikatsiyalari rivoji barcha sohalarning jadal taraqqiyotiga xizmat qiladi, odamlarga qulaylik yaratadi dedi Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Shu texnologiyalarni yanada kuchaytirish, sohani yanada jadal rivojlantirish uchun 2018-yil 19-fevraldagi "Axborot texnologiyalari va kommunikatsiyalari sohasini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"- gi farmonida ham o'z isbotini topdi. Zamonaviy ta'limni tashkil etishga qo'yladigan muhim talablardan biri ortiqcha ruhiy va jismoniy kuch sarf etmay, qisqa vaqt ichida yuksak natijalarga erishishdir. Qisqa vaqt orasida muayyan nazariy bilimlarni shakllantirish, faoliyatini nazorat qilish, ular tomonidan egallangan nazariy va amaliy bilimlar darajasini baholash o'qituvchidan yuksak pedagogik mahoratni, ta'lim jarayoniga nisbatan yangicha yondashuvni talab etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: avtomatlashtirilgan boshqaruv, modellashtirish, kibernetika, kibernetik modellashtirish.

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION MANAGEMENT

Iroda Mavlonberganova Ilhomjon qizi, Umida Mavlonberganova Ilhomjon qizi

Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz

Annotation: Since gaining independence, Uzbekistan has been developing socio-economically and joining international integration. As information develops in different areas of our society, the issue of information exchange arises. The development of modern science and technology, on the one hand, increases the amount of information, and on the other hand, leads to a loss of students' sustained interest in knowledge. Shavkat Mirziyoyev said that the development of information technologies and communications contributes to the rapid development of all spheres and creates convenience for people. This is evidenced by the Decree of February 19, 2018 "On measures to further improve the field of information technology and communications" to further strengthen these technologies, to accelerate the development of the industry. One of the most important requirements for the organization of modern education is to achieve high results in a short time without spending too much mental and physical effort. In a short period of time, the formation of certain theoretical knowledge, control over their activities, assessment of the level of theoretical and practical knowledge acquired by them requires high pedagogical skills, a new approach to the educational process.

Keywords: automated management, modeling, Cybernetics, cybernetic modeling.

Axborotni yig'ish va qayta ishlash jarayoni elektron hisoblash texnikasini qo'llash natijasida sifat jihatdan o'zgaradi. Elektron hisoblash texnikasining muhim ahamiyati shundan iboratki, u tarixiy paradoksni yechish uchun texnik baza bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Zamonaviy ishlab chiqarish, texnika va ilm-fan insondan shunday tezlik talab qiladiki, bu uning jismoniy va psixologik imkoniyatlari chegarasidan yuqori. Elektron hisoblash texnikasi katta hajmdagi axborotlarni tezlik bilan qayta ishlashni ta'minlaydi va rahbarlarga boshqaruv qarorlarini tayyorlash va qabul qilishda yordam beradi.

Elektron hisoblash texnikasining keng imkoniyatlari avtomatlashtirilgan boshqaruv tizimlarida yanada to'liq amalga oshiriladi. Ular boshqaruvning ilmiy asoslanganligini chuqurlashtiradi, chunki qarorlar qabul qilish rahbarning subyektiv fikri va hissiyotiga bog'liq emas, balki foydalanilgan amaldagi va kutilayotgan holatlarning miqdor xarakteristikalarida asoslanadi. Avtomatlashtirilgan boshqaruv tizimlari rahbariyatni katta joriy ishlarni mexanik bajarilishidan ozod qilishga va muhim istiqbolli boshqaruv masalalarini ijodiy hal qilishga e'tibor qaratishga yordam beradi. Avtomatlashtirilgan boshqaruv tizimlari boshqaruv tezkorligini oshirib, boshqaruv jarayonida insonning faol ishtirokini nazarda tutadi. Aynan inson qo'shimcha axborotni hisobga olib, turli variantlar baxosi asosida oxirgi hal qiluvchi qarorni qabul qiladi.

Zamonaviy ilm-fan va texnika insonni rad etmay va uni almashtirmay, ijtimoiy jarayonlarni boshqarishda katta rol o'ynaydi. Davriy fan-texnika yutuqlari boshqaruvni maqbullashtirish, boshqaruv muammolarini yechish jarayonlarini muvofiqlashtirishda yangi imkoniyatlarni ochadi. Tabiiyki, bu imkoniyatlar ijtimoiy munosabatlar xarakteriga bog'liq holda turlicha amalga oshiriladi.

Bu yo'nalishda elektron hisoblash texnikasining imkoniyatlari haqiqatdan ham juda katta. EHMlarni boshqaruvda yetarlicha qo'llanilmasligining sabablaridan biri shundan iboratki, ular ma'muriy tizimlar faoliyatini yaxshilash uchun ishlatiladi, lekin ijodiy masalalarni hal qilishga mo'ljallanmagan. Buni EHMlarni boshqaruvda qo'llash tajribasini o'tkazgan amerikalik tadqiqotchilar ham tan olishadi. Aynan shu yerda EHMning ulkan salohiyatli imkoniyatlari yotibdi.

Hozir yechilishi kerak bo'lgan asosiy nazariy va amaliy muammo shundan iboratki, boshqaruv bo'yicha muhim faoliyat - strategik qarorlar qabul qilishga zamonaviy boshqaruv texnikasini qanday kiritishi kerak. Bu boshqaruvda tub o'zgarish uning samaradorligini sifatli oshirish manbayi bo'ladi.

Elektron hisoblash texnikasining axborotni qayta ishlash va qarorlar qabul qilish jarayonida rolining ortishi tahlil va qarorning insoniy uslublari chetlatiladi degani emas. Bunday uslublarni sirasiga axborotni filtrlash va baholash, muqobillarini tanlash model va raqamli shakllardan foydalanish kabilar kiradi. Baholash va qaror qabul qilish uslublari keyin ham o'z ahamiyatini saqlab qoladi, lekin elektron hisoblash texnikasi ochib beradigan imkoniyatlar hisobiga boyitiladi va kuchaytiriladi.

Modellashtirish, bashorat qilish, ekspert baholash kabi ilmiy uslublarni ko'p asrlik tarixga ega. Lekin boshqaruvning zamonaviy instrumentariysini ilmiy-texnik inqilob, uning davrlik natijalari

bilan bog'lashga yetarlicha asos bor.

Kibernetik modellashtirish boshqaruvni maqbullashtirish keng imkoniyatlarini ochib beradi. Yirik olimlar hisobicha, kibernetik yondashuvning xarakterli jihati bo'lib, murakkab obyektlar asosiy parametrlarini o'rganish maqsadida ularni soddalashtirish va shu asosida ularning chuqur mohiyatini ochish hisoblanadi. Zamonaviy ilm-fan va texnika insonni rad etmay va uni almashtirmay, ijtimoiy jarayonlarni boshqarishda katta ro'l o'ynaydi. Davriy fan-texnika yutuqlari boshqaruvni maqbullashtirish, boshqaruv muammolarini yechish jarayonlarini muvofiqlashtirishda yangi imkoniyatlarni ochadi. Tabiiyki, bu imkoniyatlar ijtimoiy munosabatlar xarakteriga bog'liq holda turlicha amalga oshiriladi.

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CONVERSION IS ONE OF THE MOST EFFICIENT WAYS OF ENLARGING THE LEXICON OF MODERN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Maxkamboyeva Shahlo Abdurautovna

M.Ulugbek district, English teacher, shahlomaxkamboyeva@gmail.com

Abstract: The article deals with various aspects of conversion as one of the basic ways of English word-formation: definition and classification. The main types of conversion models are described and the frequency of their use in the language is commented on. Different types of conversion stem of the modern stage of development of the language system are analyzed. In conclusion, the enormous productive potential of conversion in the English language is determined.

Key words: Conversion, verbalization, substantivation, adjectivation, adverbialization productivity, word-stem.

Any language can be considered expressive and rich due to its vocabulary. Therefore, the ways of word derivation and word formation are researched carefully to expand the lexicon of language. The existence of a language system and its development are mainly due to the development of the word formation paradigm, the change in the existing types of word formation, and the increase or decrease in the proportion of their productivity. One of the effective ways of that is conversion which even does not need any suffix or prefix in creating new words.

The emergence of new words in the English language is carried out mainly in three ways: by borrowing from other languages; using various means of word formation (such as affixation, composition, conversion, etc), as a result of polysemy (the appearance of new, additional meanings in words already existing in the language). Word formation is “the richest source of new vocabulary in the language, and, as a result of this fact, is the object of close attention of scientists and linguists. [2.87-88]

The term “conversion” at the present stage of development of linguistics is understood as a “method of word formation without the use of special word formative affixes; a kind of transposition, in which the transposition of a word from one part of speech is used without any material change as a representative of another part of speech”. [3.33] Some researchers also use terms such as the non-affixing or root method of word formation.

Conversion as a linguistic phenomenon interested philologists as early as the first half of the 19th century (the beginning of the study of this method of word formations associated with the work of J. Greenwood and G.Sweet).

Conversion is customarily understood as “...the change in the part of speech of a form without any overt affix marking the change” as such, it has traditionally been regarded as particularly widespread in English in comparison with other languages with other word formation processes. The virtual unanimity in the definition of this concept is, however, not paralleled by the actual term given to it. “Conversion,” “functional shift,” “zero derivation,” and several variants of these have at one or

the other time competed to name this process. Such different terms as the above only the result of various perspectives from which the same process can be contemplated, and arguments for and against every one of them can be accordingly found. Thus, for example, “functional shift” is preferred in some references because it readily mirrors the adoption of new syntactic capacities by converted units. Explicit as this term is from the syntactic point of view, it also has to be admitted that, as pointed out by Tournier, it rather overlooks complete lack of change in the derivational morphology of the word that is proper to conversion, while focusing on a syntactic property common to other parallel but still clearly different word formation processes like, for example, suffixation. An opposite view is apparently held by other authors, who prefer to use the term “zero derivation” instead, thus laying emphasis on the morphological dimensions of the process, i.e., indicating that no morphological variation occurs under this operation and, by contrast, somehow overshadowing the new syntactic capacities of this units. This latter term has been particularly wide spread, probably it parallels other word formation patterns which involve word class change and thus fits an orderly structure of word-formation processes. [1.181] However, the most frequent term for this operation has clearly been “conversion.” Certain objections to it, have sometimes been raised, for example, by Adams, who rejects this term on the grounds that it may be understood, rather than as the adoption of new syntactic capacities, as implying a complete loss of the original identity of the word, like in the noun *stimulant*, nowadays hardly an adjective. Similarly, as pointed out by Lipka, it has sometimes also been proposed that the use of the term “conversion” he avoided in strictly synchronic approaches. However, current practice shows that, more often than not, this term occurs regardless of any diachronic consideration. [1.182] One way or the other, all these terms coincide in describing the operation by a lexical unit gains access to syntactic functions habitually realized by members of a word-class different than the one which that unit originally belonged, like in the following examples, where nouns become verbs, and verbs become respectively: (1) My boss faxed a letter which was very important. (2) Jimmy had a look at his toys and began crying as his plane was missing. (3) He told himself that all men are cowards when it came to a showdown with a woman.

No less difficult is the question of the types of conversion, as well as the classification of its components. In lexicology, there are four main types of conversion according to the belonging of components to certain parts of speech and, accordingly, four conversion models:

1. Verbalization (the formation of the verb). This type represents the semantic transformation of the “object” – the “action associated with this object”: *flower* (the type of a plant which is often brightly coloured with a pleasant smell) – to *flower* (to blossom, to develop completely); *water* (a clear liquid, without colour or taste, which falls from sky and is necessary for animal and plant life) – to *water* (to pour water on to plants or the soil that they are growing in); *an elbow* (the part in the middle of an arm where it bends) – to *elbow* (to push someone with your elbow);

2. Substantivation (formation of nouns). The semantic transformation of an “action” is being implemented – the “object as a result of an action” ; to look (to direct your eyes in order to see) – look (when you look at someone or something); to sleep (to be in the state of rest when your eyes are closed, your body is not active, and your mind is unconscious) – sleep (the resting state)

3. Adjectivation (formation of adjectives). The model expresses the semantic transformation of the “subject” into “characteristic phenomenon of the subject”; christian (someone who believes in Jesus Christ) – christian(relating to christianity) ; granny (grandmother)- granny(means having the style like those worn by old woman)

4. Adverbialization (education of adverbs). At the present level of development of the language system, this type is not productive due to the presence of the –ly suffix in the language. The most productive type of conversion is substantivation, and the formation of nouns from adjectives is much more common than their formation from verbs. Next comes verbalization with the frequency realization of the linking “nounverb”. The least productive are adjectival and adverbialization conversion types.

According to the degree of transfer of meaning, researchers distinguish two conversion classes: transposable and word-formation (lexical) In a transposable conversion, the denotative component of the word does not change, but only the syntactic function changes.

The basis sign of conversion as a process of the word education is the emergence of a new lexeme with lexical and grammatical content. The peculiarity of this phenomenon is the fact that there is a rethinking of the rotation of the meaning of the word- basis and its consideration in another aspect. However, one can not but agree with the fact that the word, which appeared as a result of a conversion, includes a certain semantic area of the original word-basis.

In conclusion, there are a great number of ways to expand the number of words in any language, say, adopting words from other languages, through the way of derivation, forming words and so on. Conversion is one of the most effective ways in enriching the lexicon of English language which makes it expressive. This way does not need any change to the word which makes creating new words elementary without difficulties. Among the types of conversion such as, verbalization, substantivation, adjectivation, adverbialization the type of substantivation is the most fruitful way which is seen in making nouns from different forms of speech like verbs, adjectives, etc. So, being aware of the way of conversion helps any kind of learner of English to be an eloquent speaker who express their opinion with the help of various words and word combination.

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GRAMMAR STRUCTURES WITH VOCABULARY

Sayfiddinov Islomxon Sobir o'g'li

Termiz state University

Foreign philology faculty Uzbekistan

Abstract: This article based on learning. This is so crucial for beginning learn English grammar.

Key words: grammatical rengee, articles, crucial methods

Grammar is important learning English.

Grammar is the foundation for all of our writing and speaking in English. Having a solid foundation makes it easier to achieve fluency. Native speakers can benefit from a refresher on English grammar basics, which they may have forgotten over time. Refreshing the basics is one way to help break bad habits in writing.

Parts of Speech

In English grammar, the eight major parts of speech are noun, pronoun, adjective, verb, adverb, preposition, conjunction, and interjection.

Nouns

The easy way to remember nouns is that they refer to people, places, or things. Even intangible or abstract concepts like ideas or thoughts are things. In the following sentences, the nouns are highlighted:

Sally doesn't use an iPhone . Jared doesn't eat subs . The Earth is not the center of the universe .

Pronouns

Pronouns are words that replace nouns: I, me, she, we, they, who, that, yours, his, her, etc.

Pronouns need antecedents. That means that the thing (or person, or place) that the pronoun refers to needs to have been mentioned already by name somewhere earlier in the sentence or paragraph. If it's not clear which thing the pronoun refers to, the reader can get quite confused.

I swam in the ocean. You swam in the ocean. He swam in the ocean. She swam in the ocean. It swam in the ocean.

Adjectives

Adjectives are descriptive words that add detail to a sentence. They can give important or necessary information (e.g., Please hand me the blue paper), or they can just make the sentence more interesting (e.g. A frigid wind blew around the icy town). Adjectives describe nouns. Please sew the red dress. The weather is hot and humid . The stuffed toy is fuzzy and round .

Verbs

Verbs are action words: that's a rather simplified explanation, but it's the clearest one. Verbs tell you what the subject of the sentence is up to.

He ran into the wall. She buys new shoes. The cat licks its fur.

Adverbs

Adverbs describe verbs, adjectives, or even a whole sentence. Adverbs often end with the suffix -ly (for example, badly, hungrily), but some look the same as their adjective forms (for example, the word fast is used as both an adjective and adverb).

Prepositions

Prepositions are little words that tell where or when (among other things) something is. The monkey is on his back. The glue is behind the board. The dreamcatcher is above the bed.

Conjunctions

Conjunctions are words like and, but, and or that connect concepts, clauses, or parts of sentences.

I wanted to meet her there on time, but I got stuck in traffic. You can't wear socks and sandals.

Interjections

Interjections are words like wow and yay. They're sounds we make to convey extreme emotion or to create emphasis when we're talking, sometimes when we can't think of a good way to express ourselves. The problem with interjections is that they require a great deal of context to be understood. For instance, hey can mean hello, or that's great, or stop doing that. Hey! How's it going? Wow! Those fireworks are impressive. Yay! I passed calculus!

Verb Tenses

Verbs come in past, present, and future tenses. The past is used to describe things that have already happened (e.g., earlier in the day, yesterday, last week, three years ago). The present tense is used to describe things that are happening right now, or things that are continuous. The future tense describes things that have yet to happen (e.g., later, tomorrow, next week, next year, three years from now).

Past tense I lived here when I was ten. Present tense I live here now. Future tense I will live there when I am retired.

Subject-Verb Agreement

Singular subjects take singular verbs and plural subjects take plural verbs.

(In this example, the subject is in bold and the verbs are italicized.)

My brother is a doctor. **My parents** are yoga teachers.

Pronoun-Antecedent Agreement

When a pronoun replaces a noun, the noun is called an antecedent. On Michael's first day of work, he was a little nervous. Michael is the antecedent and he is the pronoun.

The antecedent doesn't have to go before the pronoun, but in longer sentences it can be confusing to introduce the pronoun before the antecedent. On his first day of work, Michael was a little nervous.

Subjunctive Mood

The subjunctive is a form verbs can take to express conditions that are hypothetical or not true. It's not a verb tense. The subjunctive form usually uses the third-person form of the verb with the -s dropped. When using the verb "to be" in the subjunctive, the present tense is be and the past tense is were.

The subjunctive is used with certain expressions that imply a good or bad quality or an imperative. Often, the subjunctive verb is preceded by the word that (as in the phrases "it is best that," and "it is essential that").

The subjunctive mood can express conditions that are not true:

If I were queen for a day, I would eat cake for breakfast, lunch, and dinner.

It can express hypothetical situations:

If I were to design a dresser, it would be made of teak.

It can be used to express wishes:

I wish I were able to go on vacation with you.

It can express commands or demands:

The boss demanded that he complete the project or be fired.

It can express suggestions:

I suggest that she cut back on refined sugar to improve her health.

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ABU YOQUB YUSUF AL-HAMADONIY HAZRATLARINING TASAVVUFIY QARASHLARI

Sayfidinova Zarina Nabijon qizi ,Mardanov Jasurbek Davran o`g`li

¹Denov tadbirkorlik va pedagogika instituti talabasi, zarinasayfidinova1@gmail.com²Denov tadbirkorlik va pedagogika instituti talabasi, mardanovjasurbek99@gmail.com

Anotatsiya: Maqolada Movorounnahr diniy-irfoniy ta`limot asoschilaridan biri ,tasavvuf yo`nalishining yetuk vakili, Yassaviya va Xojagon(Naqshbandiya) tariqatlarining ma`naviy otasi hisoblangan Abu Yoqub Yusuf al-Hamadoniyning betakror hayot yo`li ,ilmiy me`rosi haqida ma`lumotlar tavsif etiladi

Kalit so`zlar: Tasavvuf, tariqat, fiqh, mutasavvif, sufiylik, ilm an nazar, ratsionalizm

THE MYSTICAL VIEWS OF ABU YAQUB YUSUF AL-HAMADANI

Sayfidinova Zarina Nabijon qizi, Mardanov Jasurbek Davran ugli

¹ Student of the Denau Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy, zarinasayfidinova1@gmail.com² Student of the Denau Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy, mardanovjasurbek99@gmail.com

Annotation: The article describes the unique way of life and scientific heritage of Abu Yoqub Yusuf al Hamadani, one of the Movorounnahr religious and mystical teachings ,a leading figure in the field of mysticism,the spiritual father of the Yassaviya and Khojaghan sects

Key words: Mysticism, sect, fiqh, mystic, Sufism, ilm an nazar, rationalism

Tasavvuf –islomda insonni ruhiy va axloqiy jihatdan komillik sari yo`llovchi ta`limot.Tasavvuf ta`limotiga ko`ra tanlangan insonlar (al xossa) Alloh bilan hissiy bog`lanishi mumkin.Pirovardida ular Allohni tanishga erishadi.Uning asosini zikr tashkil etib ,mafkuraviy-diniy asosi esa Qur`oni Karim va uning ma`nolari ustida chuqur mushohada yuritish ,uning botiniy ma`nolarini tahlil qilish hisoblanadi.Tasavvuf yo`liga kirgan ,bu yo`lda umrini sarf etgan kishilar esa mutasavvif deb ataladi. Movorounnahr hayotida muhim ro`l o`ynagan mutasavviflar sirasiga esa Sayf ad-din Boxarziy,,Termiz sayyidlari,Sayyid Baraka,Xoja Ahror ,Maxdumi A`zam,Mir-I arab ,Lutfulloh Chustiy va boshqa shayxlarni keltirish mumkin.Movorounnahr hududida tasavvuf yo`nalishining kirib kelishi va rivojlanishi esa Shayx Abu Yoqub Yusuf al-Hamadoniyl shaxsiyati bilan bog`liqdir.

Abu Yoqub Yusuf al-Hamadoniyl 1048-yili Hamadonning Buzanjird qishlog`ida, ko`pchilik tasavvuf adabiyotlarida qayd etilishicha islomni yangi qabul qilgan bir ma`jusiyl fors kishi oilasida tug`ilgan.Bo`lajak shayx 17 yoshligida ilm-u irfonga juda chanqoqligi boisdan ham ilm istab xalifalik poytaxti dunyodagi yetuk olimlarni o`z bag`riga jamlagan Bog`dodga keladi va u yerdagi mashhur “Nizomiya” nomli madrasada tahsil oladi.Abu Ishoq al-Sheroziyl,,Abu Is`hoq an Nazzoliyl,Xatib al-Bog`dodiyl,Abu Husayn al Muqtadiyl ka`bi olimlardan fiqh,hadis ,tasavvuf ilmlarini chuqur o`rganadi.Ayrim manbalarda qayd etilishicha uning birinchi ustozi Shayx Abu Ali Farmadiyl bo`lgan.Ushbu Shayx ham “Silsilai Sharifga` kirgan zoti shariflardan hisoblanadi.Yusuf Hamadoniyl Movorounnahr kelib ,Samarqand ,Buxoro ,Marvda o`z ta`limotini davom ettirgan.Balx va Hirotga tez -tez borib turgan.Buxoroda xonaqoh qurib o`z ta`limotidan

ommaga saboq bera boshlagan. Yusuf Hamadoniy juda ko'p shogird chiqargan. Bu yo'lda tom ma'noda zahmat chekgan, Alloh rizosi yo'lida ilmni o'zgalarga ulashgan va o'rgatgan jonkuyar ulamo desak aslo mubolag'a bo'lmaydi. Nasafiy bergan ma'lumotlarga ko'ra Abu Yoqub Yusuf al-Hamadoniy 95 yil umr ko'rgan bo'sa (ayrim manbalarda 90 yil) 38 marta piyoda ka'ba ziyoratiga borgan (ayrim manbalarda 30 marta deyiladi). Farididdin Attor o'zining "Tazkirat ul-avliyo" asarida Yusuf Hamadoniyni mashhur shayxlar qatorida eslab uni tasavvuf ta'limotining yirik namoyondasi Mansur Xalloy tarafdorlaridan biri bo'lganligini ta'kidlagan. Lekin bu ikki mutasavvif qarashlari o'rtasida o'zaro o'xshashlik mavjud emas. Manzur Xalloy asosan isyonkor ruhdagi tasavvufiy tasavvurlarni, g'oyalarni ilgari surgan bo'lsa, Yusuf Hamadoniy esa ularga yangicha hayot bag'ishlaydi.

Hamadoniy Bog'dodda yashagan kezlarida As Somoniy, Ahmad al G'azzoliy (Abu Homid G'azzoliyning akasi) ka'bi zamonasining yetuk ulamolaridan ham saboq olganligi ayrim manbalarda qayd etilgan. Shayx ushbu ulamolardan tasavvuf va tariqatga oid ko'plab ilmlarni o'rganadi. Yusuf Hamadoniy umrining ikkinchi yarmini ko'proq Hirot, Marv, Smarqand va Buxoro shaharlarida o'tkazadi. Marv va Buxoroda xonaqoh va madrasa qurdiradi va o'zining ko'plab shogirdlarini tarbiyalaydi. Ular orasida ko'plab turkiy va forsiy millatiga mansub shaxslar ham bor ekanligi olimning nechog'lik Movorounnahr hamda Xuroson ilm-u ma'rifatiga hissa qo'shganidan dalolat beradi. Hasan Andoqiy, Abdullo Baraqqiy, Ahmad Yassaviy va Abdulxoliq G'ijduvoniylar Yusuf Hamadoniyning eng ishonchli shogirdlaridan hisoblanishib ba'zi manbalarda "to'rt xalifa"si deb ham qayd etib o'tilgan. Yusuf Hamadoniy Xojai jahon Abdulxoliq G'ijduvoni va Yassaviya tariqatining asoschisi ko'pchiligimizga ma'lum va mashhur Ahmad Yassaviy singari buyuk zotlarni tarbiyalab bergan. Yana shuni ham ta'kidlab o'tish lozimki Yusuf Hamadoniy Xojagon (Naqshbandiya) tariqatining mashhur shiorlari sifatida barchaga ma'lum bo'lgan "xush dar dam", "nazar bar qadam", "safar dar vatan", "xizmat dar anjuman" ka'bi qoidalarni ishlab chiqib sufiylik amaliyotiga tadbiiq etgan. Naqshbandiya tariqatining asosiy tamoyillarini o'rnatgan Yusuf Hamadoniy talab-qoidalariga Abdulxoliq G'ijduvoni to'rtta, Xoja Bahouddin Naqshbandiy esa uchta talab-qoida joriy etib Naqshbandiya tariqatining asosiy tamoyillarini o'rnatadi. Yusuf Hamadoniy taqvodor, pokiza va nihoyatda halol inson bo'ganligi manbalarda qayd etilgan. Yusuf Hamadoniy o'zining shogirdi Abdulxoliq G'ijduvoni tomonidan barkamol inson va "shayx ash-shayx" deb tilga olinishi fikrimiz isbotidir. "Rashohot ayn-ul hayot" asarida yozilishicha Abu Yoqub Yusuf al Hamadoniy hijriy 535-yili (1140.y) Hirot dan Marvga ketayotganlarida Bomiyon (hozirgi Afg'oniston) da vafot etadi. Uning jasadini shogirdi Ibn Anjir Marvga olib keladi. Uning o'rni Xuroson va Movorounnahr tasavvuf ilmiy-falsafiy taraqqiyotida shunchalik yuqoriki hattoki uning Marvdagi qabristoni o'z davrida "Xuroson ka'basi" deb ulug'langanligi haqida ham ba'zi ma'lumotlar uchraydi.

Shogirdlari yozib qoldirgan ma'lumotlarga qaraganda Abu Yoqub Yusuf al Hamadoniy uzun bo'lyi ,xushro'y va kelishgan,ozg'in kishi bo'lgan.Haqsizlik ,munofiqlik va riyokorlik ka'bi illatlarni qattiq qoralagan.Yana bir e'tiborimizni tortgan mihim bir jihat borki uni qayd etmasdan iloji yo'q.Yusuf Hamadoniy yolg'onchi va poraxo'r,hudbin va nohaq qon to'kuvchi kishilardan qattiq g'azablanib hattoki muttahaam ,xaromxo'r ,maqtanchiq ,fosiq,dinni o'zi uchun manfaat vositasi qilib olgan betavfiq kishilarni o'z huzuriga chorlab ularga ham dashnom berib turgan ekanlar .

Shayx Abu Yoqub Yusuf al Hamadoniy falsafiy ta'limotlar sohasida ham ijod etgan bo'lib ko'pchilikni qiziqtirib kelgan modda va ruhning o'zaro munosabatlari masalasida ham chuqur mushohada ,mustaqil fikriga ega shaxs bo'lganlar

Shayx fikricha har bir mavjudotda insonning yaratilganligi va o'limga mahkum etilganligiga oid ko'pdan kop nishon va alomatlar mavjud bo'lib biz bu haqiqatni esa teran mushohada va tadabbur qilish orqaligina kuzatish mumkin.Agar kishi to'rt unsuridan biri hisoblangan tuproqning sifatiga sayohat qilinsa inson deb atalmish ulug' bir mavjudotning tuproqdan yaratilganligini ya'ni tuproqdan kelib chiqqanligini kuzatishimiz mumkin ekan.

Yusuf Hamadoniy "Ilm an nazar" ya'ni ratsionalizm sohasida ham yetuk mutaxasis bo'lib yetishadi biroq tez orada o'sha ilmdan voz kechib xudojo'ylik yo'liga kiradi.

Shayx Abu Yoqub Yusuf al Hamadoniy "Rutbat ul hayot ","Kashf","Risola dar odobi tariqat","Risola fi amal kavna masaxxarun lil-inson","Risola dar axloq va munojot" ka'bi asarlarning muallifidir.

Abu Yoqub Yusuf al Hamadoniy nazarida inson ka'bi zoti sharifning martabasi shu darajada yuksak,shu darajada yuqoriki amal daftarini yozib turuvchi ,turli vazifalarni bajaruvchi ,Arshni tutib turgan farishtalar ,nurdan , olovdan va ruhdan tashkil topgan barcha mavjudotlar hazrati Odam (alayhissalom) zoti va jamoli oldida sajda qilganlar.Shayx o'z mulohazalarini davom ettirib inson doimo Qur'oni Karimdagi hayvonlarning martabasini qoralovchi va insonlarning martabasini madh etuvchi oyatlarni takrorlab ,ular ustida chuqur mushohada etib yurishlari lozimdir.Agar doimo shunday qilib yursa inson yashashdan maqsadi, umrning ma'nosini tushunib anglab yetishi mumkin.

"Kimki nafsi do'st va karamli bo'lsa ,u kishining diniy iashlari osonlashadi"

("Rutbat ul hayot")

Abu Yoqub Yusuf al Hamadoniyning "Rutbat ul hayot" asaridan olingan yuqoridagi parchada aks etgan hikmatli so'zning botiniy ma'nolariga diqqat qiladigan bo'lsak inson nafsining inson hayotidagi o'rni va ro'li faqat salbiy emas balki agar u insonning nafsi o'ziga do'st qilib olinsa va nafsi karamli bo'lsa uning hayotida yaxshi o'rinda bo'lishi ham mumkin.Bu fikrimiz isboti sifatida valiylar,avliyolar ,Allohning do'stlari shaxsiyatiga diqqat qilish joiz.Ular bu martabaga

o'z nafsini bo'ysundirish ,bo'ysundiribgina qolmasdan balki u bilan do'st bo'lish orqali erishgandirlar.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish mumkinki Yusuf al Hamadoniy nafaqat Movorounnahr va Xuroson balki butun islom olamida ham o'zining betakror tasavvufiy qarashlari ,ilmiy merosi ,falsafiy mushohadalari orqali o'ziga xos maktab yarata olgan zotdir.Mana shunday ulug' insonlarning ilmiy-ma'naviy me'rosini o'rganish, ularni ommaga tanitish esa bugungi kun yoshlarining vazifasidir

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MUSICAL SIDES OF IBN SINO

Nargiza Aliyeva

Namangan State University

3rd year student of music education

Anotation: This article explains the views of the encyclopedic scientist Ibn Sina, who made a great contribution to the development of world science, during his short life, he left an indelible mark on all sciences with his advanced works, his views on the role of music in medicine.

Keywords: Law of Medicine, ash-shifa, alla, acoustics, rhythm, maqom, treatises on music, natoj book, encyclopedia.

IBN SINONING MUSIQIY QIRRALARI

Nargiza Aliyeva

Namangan Davlat Universiteti

Musiqiy ta'lim 3-bosqich talabasi

Anatatsiya : Ushbu maqolada, jahon fani taraqqiyotiga ulkan hissa qo'shgan qomusiy olim Ibn Sinoning qisqa umri davomida barcha fanlarda o'zini ilg'or asarlari bilan o'chmas iz qoldirgani, tabobat ilmida musiqani o'rni haqidagi qarashlari izohlab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlari:Tib qonuni, ash-shifa,alla, akustika, ritm, maqom, musiqa haqida risosalar, natoj kitobi, donishnoma.

Jahon fani taraqqiyotiga ulkan hissa qo'shgan, tabiblar tomonidan "Hakimlar otaxoni"- "Shayx-ur-ra'is", g'arbda "Avitsena" (Avicenna) nomi bilan mashhur bo'lgan, bugungi kunga qadar o'z axamiyatini yo'qotmagan 22jilddan iborat bo'lgan "Kitob ash-shifo", 5 kitobdan iborat bo'lgan "Tib qonunlari" kabi noyob asarlar muallifi bo'lgan O'rta Osiyolik buyuk qomusiy olim Ibn Sino (to'liq ismi – Abu Ali Al-Xusayn ibn Abdulloh ibn al-Xasan ibn Ali) 980-1037 yillarda yashab o'tgan.(1)

Abu Ali ibn Sino qomusiy olim sifatida o'z davridagi juda ko'p fanlarning deyarli barchasi bilan shug'illangan. Uning dunyoning juda ko'p qo'lyozma xazinalarida saqlanib kelayotgan falsafa, tabobat, fizika, ximiya, matematika,geologiya, matreologiya, astranomiya, botanika, din tarixi, musiqa, she'riyat, filologiya va boshqa fanlarga oid asarlari allomaning buyuk istedot sohibi va yirik qomusiy olim sifatida shuhrat qozonganining yorqin timsolidir. (2)

Asil ismi Abu Ali al Xusayn ibni Abdulloh ibnul Xasan ibni Ali ibn Sino 980yili Buxoro yaqinidagi Afshon qishlog'ida dunyoga keldi. 10yoshigacha Quranni yod olib bo'lgan edi, arab yozuvi, fiqx ilimlarini o'rgandi so'ng tabobatni tanlab umrini manashu ilmga sarf qildi. Ibn Sino juda yosh chog'idayoq o'tkir zehni va ilmga bo'lgan qobilyati bilan hammani hayratda qoldirgan. U 12yoshdayoq har tomonlama bilimdon bo'lib yetishgan va har xil fanlardan mashg'ulot olib borgan. O'zidan katta yoshdagi bolalar kelib,undan ta'lim oladigan bo'lgan.16 yoshdan boshlab, barcha fanlar sohasida mustaqil mutolaa qila boshladi. Bu davrda u kunduzlari tinmay, kechalari uxlamay kitob o'qishga kirishadi. Olim tib (tabobat) ilmini juda erta o'rgana boshlaydi va qisqa muddat ichida tabobat bo'yicha odamlarni ko'ziga ko'rindi, tanila boshladi. Manbaalarda tabobat xaqida shunday

yoʻzadi -"bu qisqa muddat ichida odamlar ko'ziga ko'rinib qolganimga xayron bo'lmaslik kerek, Tabobat qiyin ilm emas". Bu so'zlardan biz - Ibn Sinoning tabobatga bo'lgan qobiliyati ilohiy deyishimiz mumkin. O'zining mana shunday g'ayrioddiy, kuchli zakovati bilan tabobatni o'rgandi. Bu ilmni o'rganishdagi dastlabki ustoz Abu Abdulloh Notiliy edi. U faylasuf, mantiq ilmini sohibi bo'lib, xalq orasidagi laqabi mutafalsif - falsafachi bo'lgan. Ibn Sino ustozidan ilmi mantiq, falsafa va xandasani o'rgandi. Ba'zi falsafiy masalalarda ustozidan o'zib ketdi, so'ngra o'zi mustaqil kitoblar ko'ra boshladi-falsafa va mantiq bo'yicha. Ustoz Abdulloh Notiliy Ibn Sinodagi iqtidor va qobiliyatni ko'rganidan keyin otasiga "bu-bola ilmdan boshqa narsa bilan shug'illanmasin" deb aytadi. Otasi kerak bo'lgan barcha sharoitni yaratib berdi, Ibn Sino tinmasdan mutolaa qildi tabobatdan boshqa ilmlarni - optika ,kimyo fiqh kabilarni o'rgandi. Xusosan, tabobatga e'tiborini qaratdi. Shu bilan birga ajoyib musiqa nazriyachisi ham edi. Yuqorida aytib o'tilganidek, Ibn Sino ko'plab sohalarni qamrab o'rgandi, xusosan, mantiq, psixologiya, astranomiya, matematika, musiqa, fiqh, axloq, adabiyot, tilshunoslik va bularga doir 450dan ortiq asarlar yaratdi. Ibn Sino 60 yoshga ham kirmagan umri davomida manashunday ilmlarni o'rgandi, o'rgatdi va ularga doir yetarlicha ma'lumotlar qoldirdi. Uning o'ngan har bir sohasini bir fakultet deb olsak, Ibn Sinoni o'zi butun boshli universitet deb atashimish hato bo'lmaydi.

Ibn Sinoning "Kitobush – shifa"(Shifo kitobi), "Donishnoma"(Bilim kitobi), " Kitabun najat"(najot kitobi) kabi asarlarining musiqaga doir qismi va "Risalatun fi-ilmil-musiqiy"(Musiqa ilmi haqida risolalari) jahon musiqa fani va madaniyati tarixida alohida o'rin tutadi.

Ibn Sinoning bosh asarlaridan biri – "Kitobush - shifa " falsafiy harakterda bo'lib, unda muallifning tabiiy-ilmiy qarashlari aks ettiriladi. Muallif 13 qismda zamonasidagi tabiiy fanlarni sharhlab beradi. Shu jumladan bu yerda musiqaning nazariyasi ham yoritiladi. Asar 4 ta katta bo'limdan iborat:

1. Mantiq
2. Fizika (tabiiy)
3. Aniq fanlar
4. Metafizika

Aniq fanlardan biri musiqadir. Ibn Sino bu yerda musiqa nazariyasini atroflicha talqin etadi. Musiqa akustikasi, tovushlar, intervallar, jins(tetraxord va pentaxord) va jam'lar(turli diapazonli tovushqator), maqomlar, ritmlar va kuylar masalasi ilmiy-nazariy jihatdan chuqur asoslab beriladi. "Ash- shifa"ning musiqaga bag'ishlangan qismining tanqidiy matni Misrda 1956 yilda arab tilida nashr etilgan: Ibn Sino, Ash-shifa, jabomii ilmil-musiqiy,Qohira, 1956. Kitobning bu qismi R.D.Erlanje tomonidan fransuz tiliga tarjima qilinib, mazkur seriyada nashr etilgan; R.D'Erlanger, mazkur asar., II, III, Parij 1935 va 36.(3)

Ibn Sino musiqa haqida ilmiy-nazariy asarlar yozish bilan cheklanmadi, balki musiqaga

bag'ishlangan asarlarini meditsina kitoblarida ham aks ettirdi. Bu tasodifiy hol emas edi, albatta. Ibn Sino o'zining meditsinaga oid o'lmas asarlarida, musiqaning xissiy ta'sir kuchiga katta baho bergani holda, ruxiy kasalliklarni davolashda uni yuksak qadrladi va shifo dasturi sifatida tavsiya etdi.

Ibn Sino "Tib qonunlari" kitobida bir o'rinda musiqaning ruxiy ta'sir kuchiga baho berib, go'dakning tarbiyasidagi ahamiyatini oddiygina ta'riflaydi: "Go'dakning organizmi chiniqishi uchun ikki narsa zarur: biri uni asta qimirlatib bebratish, ikkinchisi onaning qo'shig'i(allas). Birinchisi (bolaning) tanasiga, ikkinchisi – ruxiga tegishlidir".(4)

Musiqashunos-mutaxassislar Ibn Sinoning jahon musiqasida birinchi bo'lib sof soz tizimini aniqlaganligini ko'rsatib o'tdilar. Bu haqida H.Y.Fermer - in the Journal of the Royal Asiatic society of Great Britain and Ireland junralida 1937yil Londonda nashirdan chiqqan "The lute Scale of Avicenna" ya'ni "Abu Ali Ibn Sino ud(cholg'u asbobi) pardalarining pog'onalari haqida" nomli maqolasida ajoyib holda ko'rsatib o'tgan.

Ibn Sino "Ilm – narsalarni inson aqli bilan o'rganish" deya ta'riflaydi. Qisqa umri davomida ko'plab ilm o'rgandi va amalda ilmni namoyot etdi, hamda tibbiyot ilmni chuqur o'rgangan shogirtlar ustoz bo'ldi. Umrining so'ngida bir dard keldi davolashga qancha urinsada bu ishni imkoni bo'lmadi, shogirtlari, birqancha tabiblar yig'ilishib davolamoqchi bo'lganlarida ularga qarata: -"qora tuproq qaridan tortib, to zahil cho'qqisigacha bo'lgan dunyoning hamma mushkul masalalarini xal qildim, men xar qanday makir xiyla tuzog'idan qutilib chiqdim-u ammo o'lim tugunini yecha olmadim" deya ularni tabobatga o'zi o'rgatgani haqida so'zlab umri yakunlanayotganini aytdi. Va bor davlatini sadaqa qildi, xar uch kunda hatmi Quron va zikrda bo'lib, 1037 yil 57(ba'zi adabiyotlarda 58)yoshida Hamadonda kasallikdan vafot etdi.(5)

Ibn Sinoning betakror ilmiy merosi atoqli vatandoshimizning insoniyat tarixidagi eng buyuk qomusiy olimlardan biri ekani isboti mana 900yildan oshgan vaqt davomida Ibn Sino nomi va yoki asarlarini bilmagan tanimagan o'rganmagan inson yo'qdir, desak mubolag'a bo'lmaydi.

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